

Deliverable 2.3

ROBIN Toolbox

S2I

29/12/2023

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**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

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ABBREVIATIONS

AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
BSAT	Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit
CBGMC	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Adaptation
EGD	European Green Deal
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
EPP	Environmental Protection Planning Tool
EU	European Union
QPL	Q-Plan International Advisors PC
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSES	Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy
RPO	Regional Policy Objectives
SAP	Support Action Portfolio
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
S2i	Steinbeis 2i GmbH
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
PMT	Policy Monitoring Tool

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures to accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for diverse territorial contexts. In the context of WP2 a need driven digital toolbox was developed with the aim to support the circular bioeconomy transition in a variety of regional settings.

This deliverable describes the development of the ROBIN Toolbox and its components derived from the outcomes from Task 2.3 and 2.4. The aim of ROBIN Task 2.3 was to formulate the necessary methodologies and corresponding tools to address improvement areas and support the development of new governance models and structures. The aim of T2.4 was to aggregate the information collected in T1.2 (Regional Governance Models) and T1.3 (Good Governance practices) as a knowledge platform as well as the WP2 tools and Support Action Portfolio, into a comprehensive digital toolbox available online.

The Knowledge Platform comprises a diverse collection of circular bioeconomy governance models designed for EU-wide regional implementation. It considers various typology aspects, such as governance mechanisms, constraints, territorial elements, and sustainability objectives. In addition, the good governance practices section provides practical, ready-to-use examples for streamlining the development of bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring systems and environmental protection plans. The details of the development of the Knowledge Platform information are described in D1.1 "Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models" and D1.2 "Good Governance Practices".

Regarding the ROBIN tools, the following have been developed: 1) the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas facilitates policy development as a co-design tool, allowing regional policymakers to explore governance models and structures, 2) The Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool which provides a mean to assess governance models concerning environmental, social, and governance factors and 3) The Environmental Protection Planning Tool which focuses on evaluating pollution and habitat disruption, offering a structured approach to assess environmental conditions with a set of 32 indicators. The detailed description of the development of the tools is presented in this report.

The Support Action Portfolio (SAP) provides valuable examples of capacity-building support for regions. It encompasses 49 inspirational actions categorized into regional analysis measures, social measures, and technical measures. The details of the development of this component is covered in the D2.2 "ROBIN Regional Governance Models".

The digitalization of the toolbox ensured user-friendly access, employing features like SEO optimization, search functions, a content management system, social media integration, privacy, and compliance measures, among others. The first version of the toolbox is available on the project website. Further updates and fine-tuning are planned in WP3 (T3.3) based on insights gained from testing activities.

1. Introduction

The ROBIN Toolbox is developed to support regional partners in implementing their governance models and structures. It includes three main components: i) Knowledge Platform; ii) ROBIN Tools; and iii) Support Actions Portfolio (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Structure of the ROBIN Toolbox

The comprehensive description of each component is detailed in Section 1 “Development of the toolbox components” and the implementation of the digitalisation is explained in Section 2 “ROBIN Digital Toolbox”. The main information inputs for the toolbox development derived from the outcomes of the project tasks T1.2, T1.3 and T2.3, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Information flow for the development of the ROBIN Toolbox

The improvement of the ROBIN toolbox is planned for enhancement and updates during the testing activities of Work Package 3. Collaborating with relevant stakeholders, ROBIN partners will identify usability nuances, solicit feedback on toolbox functionality and its components, with the goal of enhancing the overall user experience.

2. Development of the toolbox components

2.1 Regional Bioeconomy Governance Models

An overview of regional circular bioeconomy governance strategies and models in the EU-27 and a typology of regional bioeconomy governance models along ten dimensions was developed and is explained in detail in Deliverable D1.1 “Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models”, this was based on a sample of 20 circular bioeconomy case studies. From these results, 20 practical factsheets (Table 1) with information on Bioeconomy Governance Models were created to be included in the Knowledge Platform section of the ROBIN Toolbox.

The methodological approach employed to collect the data on regional bioeconomy models included a literature review through desk research and a data collection survey. The data collected referred to 61 models which were analysed to identify the 20 model case studies to further focus on. The research focused on identifying bioeconomy and circular bioeconomy models in the regions of EU-27 and EU Associated countries. It predominantly focused on active or planned models and strategies, but also considered some models that have been recently completed. Although the focus was at the regional level, some national models were included, either for small countries or in cases where no regional model was available.

Table 1. Selected Regional Bioeconomy Governance Models for the toolbox

#	Description
GM1	Green Synergy Cluster – Cluster Zelena Sinergiya
GM2	Resilient Thessaloniki
GM3	Circular Biobased Delta
GM4	Regional Innovation Strategy Sachsen-Anhalt 2014-2020
GM5	BioökonomieREVIER
GM6	Bavaria´s Bioeconomy Strategy
GM7	Alliance Plant ³
GM8	Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy
GM9	Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia
GM10	Circular Economy Strategy Castilla y Leon
GM11	Plan to boost to the agri-food bioeconomy Castilla y Leon
GM12	Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024 Basque Country
GM13	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation
GM14	North Sweden Cleantech
GM15	The Bioeconomy Strategy of the Inland Region Norway 2017-2024
GM16	The Arctic Smart & Circular Economy Cluster
GM17	Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan
GM18	Circular Economy Strategy Luxembourg
GM19	South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy
GM20	Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana

For an analogue version each model document factsheet template was developed (Figure 3). Each factsheet contains the following information:

1. Governance model name
2. Country / Region
3. Executive summary
4. Type of strategy
5. Governance model description
6. Territorial aspects
7. Key actors
8. Environmental objectives
9. Societal objectives
10. Economic objectives
11. Transformation path
12. Enabling Governance Mechanisms
13. Constraining Governance
14. Driver Measures
15. Focus
16. Further Information

Figure 3 Example of a ROBIN Governance Model Factsheet

2.2 Good Governance Practices

MTU compiled a catalogue of 75 good governance practices for supporting local operators and innovation developers in the circular bioeconomy. These practices were drawn from across six geographical regions in Europe, supporting different stakeholder groupings, and covering a multitude of different support types, including policy innovation, education and awareness, business models, social innovations, networking, financial supports and many more. Based on previously international definitions from ENRD (2018) and FAO (2013), good practices were defined as such based on their ability to demonstrate positive results, their transferability of replication potential, and their testing or validation in operational environments. The detailed description of this development can be found in ROBIN Deliverable D1.2 “Good Governance Practices”.

From the initial compilation of 75 practices have been documented 10 of these were further developed into case studies, included within D1.2. In addition to ensuring alignment with the definition of good practice, consideration was given to ensuring good diversity of practice within the 10 case studies, such that a broad range of case studies could be provided for consideration by

regions. This included the need to ensure that models associated with different types of practices, and covering different territorial contexts were represented within the case studies. These 10 case studies have also been selected for inclusion within the toolbox, as inspiring examples for regions to consider. The selected practices are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Selected Good Governance practices for the toolbox

#	Title
GGP1	Region of Skåne’s Innovation-oriented public procurement program
GGP2	Greve Biogas “Magic Factory”
GGP3	Biovoices: Video shorts in social media
GGP4	BIOVALE Innovation Camp
GGP5	Italian Ban on single use carrier bags
GGP6	Grand Est Bioeconomy Eco System
GGP7	Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Congress
GGP8	National Procurement Database for Biobased Products
GGP9	Edible Landscape Project CLG
GGP10	Funding programmes regarding bioeconomy topics in Baden Württemberg

For an analogue version each model document factsheet template was develop (Figure 4). Each factsheet contains the following information:

1. Good practice name
2. Country / Region
3. Executive summary
4. Type of practice
5. Good Governance Practice Description
6. Deployment Setting
7. Stakeholders / Beneficiaries
8. Environmental Impact
9. Social Impact
10. Economic Impact
11. Further Information

Good practice name	REGION OF SKÅNE'S INNOVATION-ORIENTED PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PROGRAM
Country / Region	Sweden / SKÅNE
Executive summary	Skåne Introduced an Innovation-oriented procurement programme focused on the sustainable procurement of bio-based aprons as a mechanism to reduce healthcare emissions.
Type of practice	Fiscal & Financial
Good Governance Practice Description	The good practice is situated in the region of Skåne, in Sweden, Skåne's experiences proximity to cross-border regions, especially near the Öresund Strait, and the region also occupies a strategic location as a hub between Scandinavia and continental Europe. The Öresund strait area is named after the body of water separating Sweden and Denmark and is bounded by Skåne and the Danish capital region, Zealand. The Öresund strait area is the most densely populated area in Scandinavia, with good transport links such as road and rail tunnels, and strong economic and geographic links across the strait. Skåne's region has moved away from traditional manufacturing dependence, towards greater reliance on services that have to do with human capital such as real estate, business services and financial intermediation. This shift has increased employment and productivity in these sectors. Skåne's economy contributed significantly to the economic growth of Sweden, until the financial crisis associated with the Great Recession. Until 2007, Skåne's economic growth was close to Sweden's average and generated around 12% of the country's economic growth. Skåne's economy was hit particularly hard in the first two years of the Great Recession but since then appeared healthy in comparison to the Swedish average. Unemployment rates recovered somewhat well, even though they were relatively high due to population growth and immigration from other Swedish regions.
Deployment Setting	Urban
Stakeholders / Beneficiaries	Public Bodies

Figure 4 Example of a ROBIN Good practices

2.3 Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

2.3.1 Introduction

An important function of the ROBIN project is to support Europe's regional authorities to play a crucial role of agents of just, inclusive, and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures and models in ways that accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomies. Since each bioeconomy is unique based on the primary sources and sectors of the regions, each bioeconomy vision and strategy will have its own specificities. Moreover, since a circular bioeconomy will require the participation of multiple actors from the bioeconomy, to develop and implement these new value chains, it is important that the voices of these stakeholders are reflected within the bioeconomy vision and strategy for their region.

The CBGMC aims to be a strategic co-creation tool that will allow each region to describe, design, challenge and invent a regional vision, and identify support activities required to implement this vision. This will be specific to each region. The CBGMC co-creation tool should be designed for use by regional policymakers in collaboration with key bioeconomy stakeholders from the region. The CBGMC should support stakeholders to co-develop their regional vision, and to understand the different important aspects for its implementation.

Within the development the CBGMC, ROBIN project partners MTU and the Southern Regional Assembly followed a defined methodology with several steps including:

- Literature review that assessed the current state of knowledge.
- Benchmarking the ROBIN proposal phase CBGMC iteration against several Bioeconomy Governance Strategies researched and outlined as case studies in ROBIN Deliverable 1.1.
- Prototyping a draft tool and testing the tool with informed circular bioeconomy experts within the Task 2.1 co-creation workshops.
- Updating the tool based on user feedback.

2.3.2 Literature review

I. Existing relevant research projects

Power4Bio: The EU Horizon 2020 funded project, Power4Bio: Regions for Bioeconomy which ran until March 2021, aimed to empower EU regions to 'maximize the use of their locally available biomass feedstock', and support a bioeconomy transition through a catalogue of business model pathways to fully realize the potential of each of the 10 participating regions. Within this remit the project developed a Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit (BSAT). Integrating the various supporting materials accumulated and developed within the Power4Bio project, the toolkit provides information and solutions with tested potential for market uptake in the fields of bioenergy, biomaterials, biochemicals and food and feed. As with the ROBIN project, the BSAT toolkit is aimed at regions with differing levels of bioeconomy maturity and the principal aim is to assist decision makers to review the status of their regions and act as a guide developing regional bioeconomy strategies (Power4Bio, 2021). Unlike the Power4Bio tools, the CBGMC will have a greater focus on facilitating co-design among multiple partners which will have to be considered during digitization of the tool.

BioSTEP: Identifying the critical need for stakeholder dialogue in the future development of the bioeconomy, BioSTEP aims to mobilize and engage with stakeholder groups regarding that future by increasing access to bioeconomy knowledge and information. Applying a three-tier approach to engage stakeholders through bespoke communication tools (workshops, conferences, exhibitions,

and public debates), BioSTEP applied a 'living lab approach' to encourage the stakeholder groups involvement in bioeconomy business model development.

Like the ROBIN project, BioSTEP follows a participatory approach towards bioeconomy development. The three-tiered approach attempts to overcome the complexity of involving the various stakeholder groups. Within this approach the project has the following objectives:

- Developing an improved bioeconomy understanding, including the benefits and consequences.
- Increasing stakeholder engagement.
- Sharing best practices amongst the stakeholder groups (including policy makers)
- Sharing existing data on bio-based products amongst the wider public as well as stakeholder groups.

Whilst the ROBIN project and the CBGMC are more focused towards partnerships at a regional governance level and towards the development of policy, there is synergy with BioSTEP in the need for multistakeholder interaction and development of a long-term bioeconomy development strategy.

BIOVOICES: The BioVoices project, whilst not specifically policy-driven like the ROBIN project, holds relevance as it was a project that fostered communication between stakeholder groups through a specifically created platform. The project developed a platform that encouraged the engagement of all the targeted stakeholder groups to share the different knowledge, experience and perspectives and the mutual learning opportunities that arise from this, something which is important for the co-design nature of the CBGMC tool.

As the name of the project suggests, BioVoices aims to foster awareness within the wider community of the bioeconomy and the benefit of bio-based products, by using a defined set of actions:

- A knowledge platform
- Events & Workshops
- Social Media campaigns
- Information app

Using the quadruple helix model of civil society/users, industry, researchers, and public authorities, BioVoices targeted the stakeholder groups to improve the quality, relevance, know-how and social acceptability of bio-based products. This approach of stakeholder engagement is relevant to the areas of the CBGMC which seeks stakeholder input to developing the regional bioeconomy vision and further developing actionable, realistic, and achievable support actions (Biovoices, 2021).

MPOWERBIO: the MPOWERBIO project focused on empowering clusters to support companies in overcoming the valley of death. Many SMEs face challenges in attracting investment even if they have a good bio-based product or idea. MPOWERBIO supports these companies in improving how they pitch their ideas, developing a strong business plan, a clear strategy, and a well-defined customer base to attract investors. Clusters can play an important role in supporting SMEs towards investment, but sometimes need support themselves, to effectively support the companies. MPOWERBIO has established a series of train-the-trainer workshops aimed at clusters across Europe focused on supporting clusters to understand how their SME's can attract investment. To inform their support offerings, the project used a co-design approach to build/design MPOWERBIO's capacity building and business support programmes while also analysing the skill gaps and training needs of clusters. A customized template was developed for the collection of stakeholder ideas in the co-design approach. To participate in the established programme the SME's perform a self-assessment, which is subsequently evaluated by the clusters, and this is followed by the development of a tailored action plan for the applicant SME identifying the relevant supports to improve investor readiness. The Business Support Program developed by MPOWERBIO includes services for SME's and clusters

such as pitching competitions, e-learning materials, bioeconomy bootcamps etc. (MPowerBio, 2020) The approaches of MPowerBio in co-designing their programme based on the specific needs of the SME's can be related to the co-creation of the activities which support the realization of the regional vision within the CBGMC. Moreover, the project activities could provide an interesting synergy or blueprint for regional activities which aim to promote or stimulate innovation among SMEs and clusters within their circular bioeconomies.

BIOWAYS: The 24-month BIOWAYS project ran from 2016 to 2018 and focused on increasing the public awareness of bio-based products and applications to support the growth of the EU bioeconomy. The project activities aimed at developing excellent promotional and educational materials as well as designing and implementing public engagement activities, based on this material. Some tools developed for this purpose included (BIOWAYS, 2018):

- The BioWatch Platform - a publicly accessible, collaborative digital platform, to raise the profile of biobased products and industry across Europe and beyond encouraging interaction between them and the public.
- The BIOWAYS e-Library - Development of content and collection of documents that would help to improve public knowledge about bio-based products and the bioeconomy.
- Training and tools - Development of training material prepared for different application areas by targeting different groups, with particular attention to students from primary schools, secondary schools, University & PhD students, adults without any specific educational prerequisite or attending vocational courses. Tools included serious games, educational videos, educational multi-media presentations, bio-based product fact sheets, bio-art panels, and many more. For example, the BIO WHAT? Tool is a serious game developed by BIOWAYS which was inspired by the Super Mario game, which takes the player on a fun-packed adventure on which he/she will encounter all sorts of enemies and traps (the fossil-based products).

While the CBGMC serves as a co-creation tool for shaping a regional vision for bioeconomy development within the regions, the BIOWAYS tool can be an interesting support in the promoting the role of bio-based products in everyday life and improving the awareness of these innovations among the public. Depending on the established regional vision, public stakeholders will be a key actor to mobilise in regions, and the BIOWAYS tool could be an effective tool or channel to target this audience, and to boost market uptake and revenue streams from these materials.

RRI2SCALE was a three-year Horizon 2020 SwafS project (Grant Agreement No 872526), implemented the period 2020-2022, that seek to embed RRI values in the policy-making processes of four European regions, namely Vestland (Norway), Overijssel (the Netherlands), Kriti (Greece) and Galicia (Spain). RRI2SCALE developed a guidebook to support policymakers involving citizens in designing policies related to technology sectors, such as smart cities, energy, and transport. It proposed a five-phase methodology for preparing, running, and evaluating such a process (Angelidou & Politis, 2023). That guidebook and in particular the participatory approach it suggests, served as an inspiration to the development of the CBGMC tool. The CBGMC tool can be used internally by regional authorities, but it can also be used in co-creation activities with the participation of stakeholders.

II. Existing relevant tools and approaches

Business Model Canvas: The Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010) is aimed at assessing and diagnosing a business from a commercial point of view. Organized across nine fundamental building blocks that can be categorized into the areas of Feasibility, Desirability and Viability, the business model canvas helps to visualize the entire business model on a single page. The Business Model Canvas can be seen as a strong foundation to development of the CBGMC

since certain building blocks of the canvas, can be equally relevant when considering the development of a regional bioeconomy, such as partners, resources, activities, and cost structure.

Triple Layered Canvas: The Triple Layered Business Model Canvas (Joyce & Paquin, 2016) could be considered an evolution towards sustainability orientated business models. As the name suggests this canvas adds two additional layers to the business aspect. The Environmental layer is based upon a lifecycle assessment perspective and a Social Layer that brings the stakeholder's perspective into the equation. Like the Business Model Canvas, the Triple Layered Business Model Canvas is foremost a tool to develop a business plan for a commercial enterprise to develop a revenue stream. Whilst accommodating environmental and social issues, it should be remembered that the CBGMC aims are more holistic in its purposes and aims to be a tool to aid the development of the regional bioeconomy strategy for the region.

Donut Economics Model:

Further incorporating social, environmental, and economic factors, The Donut Economics model (Raworth, K. 2012) presented in Figure 5 consists of two concentric circles outlining a social foundation and an ecological ceiling, with the premise that a safe and just space for humanity can exist in between the two. The social foundation consists of factors like energy, water, food, social equity, gender equality etc. Whereas the ecological ceiling encompasses the areas of climate change, air pollution, biodiversity loss, chemical pollution etc. This model is particularly interesting as many of the aspects also exist within the EU Bioeconomy Strategic Objectives, and therefore aligns with the CBGMC aims.

Figure 5 Donut Economics Model

III. Existing relevant frameworks and strategies

EU Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework: The EU Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework and system, which has been established since 2019, collects and provides comprehensive, robust, and reliable information to monitor all areas of the bioeconomy. It has become a vital tool to enable policymakers to establish targets and monitor developments related to key bioeconomy priorities. It allows a broader set of stakeholders, including society, to access key data related to different dimensions of the bioeconomy. Its interactive dashboard allows stakeholders to view and track the bioeconomy's progress towards sustainability in the EU and its Member States, and it remains up to date with continual collaboration between the JRC and other experts at EU and Member State level. The bioeconomy Monitoring Framework builds upon the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and encompasses different dimensions of the bioeconomy within its conceptual framework, including primary production sectors, the bioeconomy value chains which use these resources to bring new products to the market, and the three sustainability pillars of sustainability (economic, social, and environmental). From this framework, the monitoring sets out a broader set of indicators which align, where possible, with the above dimensions. In addition, to ensure that a full picture of sustainability is portrayed, each indicator is related to one of the five objectives of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy namely:

- Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security.
- Managing Natural Resources Sustainably.
- Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad.
- Mitigating and adapting to climate change.
- Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.

Building on this approach and to ensure that a holistic vision of sustainable bioeconomy is achieved, the CBGMC attempts to ensure that it is designed with these different dimensions in mind. The EU Bioeconomy Strategy objectives are broken down further into normative criteria (varying numbers depending on the objectives) which are also further broken-down key components. This shows the importance, guidance, and the breadth of scope that these indicators can provide when the CBGMC is used as a diagnostic tool for a given region.

Deploying the Bioeconomy in the EU. A framework approach for bioeconomy strategy development:

Based around the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework (outlined previously) this report provides 10 policy recommendations for supporting national bioeconomies towards a fair and just, climate neutral Europe (Barrett et al., 2021). The report identifies the need for targeted national bioeconomy strategies and / or action plans but aligning these to develop benefits and opportunities for rural, coastal, regional, and urban areas. The following 10 Key Policy Messages have been developed to guide strategy development:

Getting Started:

1. Ensuring stronger recognition of the importance of bioeconomy policy by decision-makers and stakeholders.
2. Moving from a bioeconomy concept to developing a vision.
3. Creating spaces for building collective bioeconomy awareness and leadership.

Building Transformative Coalitions:

4. Coordinating across government and across different levels of government to support bioeconomy strategy design and development.
5. Identification of existing bioeconomy initiatives for building a coherent action plan.
6. Establishing collaborative bioeconomy partnerships for co-investment.

Steering the Process:

7. Developing linkages and pathways between bioeconomy policy, funding and national and EU strategic research, infrastructure, innovation, and investment agendas.
8. Addressing the concerns and resistance of incumbent industries and patterns of behavior of citizens and consumers.
9. Encouraging diffusion of bio-based knowledge, innovation & technological advances to support rural and regional development.
10. Evaluating and gauging progress to help steer development of sustainable, circular bioeconomy's.

Overall recommendations from this report and the 10 key policy recommendations will provide key areas of development guidance to the CBGMC. Whilst all recommendations will have an influence the first three recommendations which fall under the umbrella 'getting started' align with the objectives of the canvas particularly recommendation 2 which focuses on *“Moving from a bioeconomy concept to developing a vision”*.

Scenario Exploration System: Future transitions for the Bioeconomy towards Sustainable Development and a Climate-Neutral Economy: The Scenario Exploration System (SES) developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), is a board game approach created to investigate the use of scenarios from foresight studies, with the intention of enabling policymakers and stakeholders to actively engage with foresight scenarios in an interactive process enabling participants to develop an overarching and long-term perspective (Fritsche et al., 2022). Of particular relevance to the CBGMC, the SES considers visions and strategies with several stakeholder personas including Primary Producer, Consumer, Policy Maker, Business, and Public Voice. The multiple drivers from these scenarios highlight the impacts that changing scenarios and landscapes can have on policy development and vice versa.

IV. Literature Review: Key Learnings

Previous projects illustrated the importance of tools that understand the differing levels of bioeconomy maturity, as seen in the BSAT toolkit, and the importance of being able to identify the gaps that could exist through differing scenarios, as demonstrated in the JRC's Scenario Exploration System. However, in addition to these critical aspects, several policy frameworks and strategies and some projects, e.g., BioVoices, highlight participatory involvement, addressing all stakeholder groups, in the development of circular bioeconomy governance. The CBGMC should be adaptable to differences in bioeconomy maturity, and support identification of "gaps" or needs for realization of development scenarios and should also reflect the importance of stakeholder participation in circular bioeconomy development.

The Business Model Canvas was a strong foundation for the development of the CBGMC, while the triple layer business model canvas also brought in more holistic learnings as it accommodates environmental and social issues. The EU Bioeconomy Strategy a holistic set of objectives, while the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework provided a comprehensive set of indicators linked to the 5 objectives (listed above), that must be taken into account by regions when establishing their region bioeconomy visions.

2.3.3 Benchmarking

To evaluate the structure of the first iteration of CBGMC and evaluate the priorities of existing regional governance models, a benchmarking exercise was undertaken across governance strategies outlined in Deliverable 1.1. The following regional governance models and strategies were reviewed for the purposes of the benchmarking process:

- Circular Economy Strategy 2021-2030: Castilla y León, Spain
- Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024: Basque Country/Euskal Hurria, Spain:
- The Bioeconomy Strategy of the Inland Region 2017-2024: Inland Region, Norway:
- Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan: Pays de la Loire, France
- Circular Economy Strategy Luxembourg, Lenzburg
- Regional Innovation Strategy 2014-2020, Sachsen-Anhalt, German
- Bavarian Bioeconomy Strategy, Bayern, Germany
- Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, Andalucía, Spain
- Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia, Catalunya, Spain

Key learnings considered for the tool development: The overall holistic nature of priorities is reflected within all the strategies analyzed, while the participation of diverse stakeholder groups in the development of a number of these strategies can also be identified. Whilst some prioritize strategies certain areas over others, this is largely due to regional priorities, resources, and existing infrastructure (which should also be a learning and reflected within CBGMC). Environmental and Social aspects are prominent throughout the strategies, particularly within the Andalusian Circular

Bioeconomy Strategy and Circular Economy Strategy of Castilla y León with economic objectives and considerations more prominent within the strategies of Bavaria and Luxembourg. The attention to environmental and social dimension within all the regional strategies shows the inherent importance of environmental and social aspects to the circular bioeconomy and its development. This reflects current strategic priorities as outlined in the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. Specific social issues and considerations feature prominently among the strategies analysed, particularly the areas of just transition, consumer awareness and sentiment, training, employment, and food security. These are interrelated with environmental economic issues and objectives. Decision makers using the CBGMC should keep social issues to mind as well as environmental and economic, whilst their regional vision and supporting actions. The importance of an array of regional aspects including partnerships, resources & infrastructure, budgets, revenue streams, and communication channels is evident from the regional policies analysed. These are all important elements to be considered towards the development of the tool, particularly through an environmental, economic, and social lens.

2.3.4 *Development of the CBGMC Tool*

I. Prototype development

To further develop the CBGMC towards a prototype format, MTU collaborated with regional governance partner the SRA. The SRA bring a unique understanding of regional governance having published the Southern Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for their region in 2020(2023). As has been the case in many of the existing bioeconomy strategies, the inclusion of experts from diverse backgrounds and sectors, can help in ensuring that a holistic and suitable vision can be achieved. The participation of MTU alongside SRA, ensured that different perspectives and experiences could be harnessed, taking into account the requirements of the tool to be implemented at regional level by policymakers, alongside local stakeholders.

The CBGMC prototype would also be used in Co-creation workshops at regional level as part of T2.1, as a first test, providing the developers with some feedstock on its effectiveness, with further feedback provided through alpha and beta testing with stakeholders in WP3.

II. Development of a holistic framework

The literature review sought to analyze current knowledge and understanding of the area of circular bioeconomy governance models by looking at previous relevant tools and projects, previous canvases and approaches and reports.

To support a holistic sustainable bioeconomy vision, encompassing environmental, societal, and economic sustainability, the EU Bioeconomy Strategy has developed five clear objectives, which have also been considered in the development of the EU's Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework.

The objectives, along with the key insights gained from the literature review, including the review of existing regional bioeconomy strategies and frameworks were seen as essential factors in guiding the development of sustainable regional bioeconomy strategies. Therefore, ensuring the alignment of the CBGMC design to these aspects was a priority. To begin the design process, a CBGMC framework, presented in Figure 6, was developed by MTU and SRA. The involvement of a regional government partner within the design process enabled the testing of different priorities and ideas, to ensure this aligned with the focus of the region, and this could be transferrable to the other NUT2 regions. Regional considerations were kept to the fore. For example, alignment with the regions, Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy (RSES), a long-term, strategic development framework for the future physical, economic, and social development of the Southern Region was considered (Southern Regional Assembly, 2020). Along with the categories outlined by the EU Bioeconomy

Strategy, a further 3 categories were included within the framework based on the review of regional bioeconomy strategy, and other regional considerations proposed through engagement with SRA:

- Social Benefits – including factors such as improved health, increased local employment, reduction of energy poverty, social enterprises, inclusion of socially disadvantaged sectors and gender equality.
- Environmental Benefits – including cleaner atmosphere, proper waste management, protection of biodiversity and alignment with key Climate Goals.
- Regional Benefits – including development of a diverse base of smart economic specialisms across regions, ability to attract and retain young talent in the region, engagement with regional stakeholders across government, academia, community, and industry.

Figure 6 Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework

III. Draft Canvas development

The next step of the process was to develop a CBGMC which reflected the elements of the framework. The CBGMC would be used within ROBIN regional co-creation workshops (Task 2.1) aimed at identifying activities to be included in the regional support action plans as well as shaping relevant aspects of the improved/new governance models per region. This would also be an opportunity to test a first draft version of the CBGMC.

From the literature review, the Business Model canvas was first explored to assess the relevant building blocks that could be included within the CBGMC. A structure similar to a business model canvas was selected for CBGMC so that the relevant elements of the regional bioeconomy could be captured within a single template. Certain building blocks such as partners, resources, channels and activities, were deemed essential building blocks to document a regional bioeconomy similar to a business model canvas. A key differentiator between the CBGMC and a business model canvas,

was the necessity to deliver a tool that enables the design of a holistic vision for regional bioeconomy governance models in a co-creation approach among regional stakeholders. In a traditional business model canvas, value proposition is what distinguishes a business from its competitors and is the collection of products and services a business offers to meet the needs of its customers. In the case of CBCMC, this is instead replaced by a regional vision (value proposition), which allows stakeholders to identify what it aims to achieve which will contribute to building its regional bioeconomy. Building on evidence from the triple-layered canvas, EU bioeconomy strategy and monitoring system, and the CBGMC Framework, this vision should bring environmental, social and economic benefits to the region, and this should be documented by stakeholders when identifying their regional vision. On the left-hand side of the canvas, a segment is included for the list of activities which are required to deliver the regional vision, these are co-created with the participating stakeholders. The left-hand side also identifies the partnerships, resources and infrastructure that the region has to offer. This is important since, the bioeconomy generally requires participation of a broad range of stakeholders, from biomass suppliers, to end users and many stakeholders in between, while resources, including bioresources as well as infrastructure such as biorefineries, bioenergy plants, roads, mills and many others are required (some which may already exist). The requirement to deliver regional benefits is captured on the right-hand side of the canvas, where stakeholders should note the regional development requirements which are needed to implement the vision, but which also offer benefits to the region, such as an upskilled workforce, or the development of various supporting services. Stakeholders will also note the regional development policy, which will capture the policy requirements and benefits from implementing the regional vision.

The Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas should be seen as a strategic co-creation tool that will allow each region to describe, design, challenge and invent a regional vision, and identify support activities required to implement this vision. This will be specific to each region. This tool can be continuously updated as the region's circular bioeconomy develops. The first version of the canvas is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Initial Draft Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

IV. Tool testing in co-creation workshops

The initial draft version of the CBGMC (Figure 7) was provided to ROBIN partners, with a view to using the tool, in the co-creation workshop of T2.1. ROBIN partners were supported by a webinar to discuss the implementation of the tool in the workshop setting. The tool was then used by the 5 ROBIN regions to co-create new governance models, establish their Regional Visions, and set of supporting actions to be implemented in order to achieve the vision. These steps are further described in D2.1 and D2.2.

Based on user feedback from the workshop, some final modifications were made to the canvas in order to finalize the initial draft version. In particular, stakeholders found it confusing to distinguish between (3) partnerships and (6) regional actors/stakeholders on the canvas, while (7) regional relationships was also a challenge for stakeholders to comprehend. In general, the view was that despite the differences between these as specified in the initial guidelines, there was quite a lot of overlap between some of these segments, so segment 3 has been retained in the updated draft CBGMC (Figure 7 below), while segments 6 and 7 have been replaced. At the same time, it was identified, that while there was a focus on the existing infrastructure and resources of the region, there was insufficient focus on identifying further investment requirements to achieve the regional vision. These related issues have been included within the updated CBCGM draft canvas under the new segment (6) budget cost structure. While a new segment (7), has been added to document the potential revenue streams that can help to justify the required investment, bringing opportunities to local companies, organizations, and social innovations of different sizes. The final draft canvas is presented alongside the user guidelines in Section 1.3.5 below.

2.3.5 Tool Guidelines

The ethos of the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas presented in Figure 8 below is based upon the EU Bioeconomy Objectives, these five objectives should be considered when developing the regional vision and support activities and completing and revisiting the canvas as the regional bioeconomy develops (Figure 8).

FOOD & NUTRITION SECURITY <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Food security and nutrition supported	MANAGE NATURAL RESOURCES SUSTAINABLY <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ecosystem capacity to produce services is maintained or enhanced	REDUCE DEPENDENCE ON UNSUSTAINABLE RESOURCES <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Resource efficiency improved	MITIGATE & ADAPT TO CLIMATE CHANGE <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued	STRENGTHEN EUROPEAN COMPETITIVENESS & CREATE JOBS <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Economic development fostered
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Figure 8 EU Bioeconomy Strategy Objectives

Figure 9 Final Draft Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

Canvas Progression

Whilst it is intended that completion of the canvas be done left to right (except for supporting activities, which may be identified after the vision has been identified), it is advised that as subsequent sections of the canvas are completed, others are revisited and adjusted as required.

1. Regional Vision

The Regional Vision is the integrated goal/aim that will contribute towards the development of the regional bioeconomy and contribute towards long-term environmental, economic, and social growth within the region. This will vary from region to region, but may include a combined regional bioeconomy, a functioning regional governance structure etc. In establishing the regional vision, the following aspects should be considered:

- Environmental Benefits – e.g., Cleaner atmosphere, better waste management, etc.
- Economic Benefits – e.g., Smart Specializations, attracting & retaining young talent in the region, etc.
- Social Benefits – e.g., Improved level of societal health, reduction of energy poverty, etc.

2. Activities

Activities describes the supporting activities or actions which will be required to implement the regional vision forming a regional action plan. Areas such as increasing stakeholder engagement, developing regional bioeconomy business plans, implementing environmental protection plans, or increasing bioeconomy skills development are some activities that could be considered, and these will be specific and unique to each region. Examples of the types of activities that a region could undertake to underpin the regional vision can be found in the ROBIN Support Action Portfolio (D2.2).

3. Partnerships

Partnerships describes the actors within the region that are required to collaborate to execute the regional vision. These may include Regional and Local Authorities, Civil Society, Research Institutes etc. The quadruple helix or Penta helix model can be a good consideration of the types of stakeholders who may be required (Patrick Barrett, 2021)

4. Resources

The users should identify the unique resources that are available to each specific region that are needed for deployment of the regional vision and the development of the regional bioeconomy. This will include the availability of biological resources, innovations, and R & D (and knowhow) within the region.

5. Infrastructure

Within the canvas, due to the nature of the bioeconomy, infrastructure has been allocated its own segment, separate from other resources. This covers the existing infrastructure which could be used to support the development of the bioeconomy such as pilot plants, industrial bio-refineries or bioenergy plants, or other existing relevant industrial infrastructure.

6. Budget Cost Structure

This section relates to the costs or expenses, whether they are fixed or variable, that the region will incur in changing the regional economy towards one that is centered on more bio-based and sustainable activities, and the aims of each unique regional vision. This will include impacts on labor within the region, both skilled and unskilled, land and machinery usage and the various material inputs feeding into enterprises across the region.

7. Revenue Streams

All activities within the regional bioeconomy supply potential revenue streams. These include established Food, Forestry & Marine sectors that may be providing existing biomaterials, biochemicals, biofuels, and bioenergy and could be further developed and expanded through the regional vision. The development of the regional bioeconomy through the regional vision should also impact upon all enterprises across the regional economy - whether it's Micro Enterprises, SMEs, or Multinational Firms, opportunities will arise for innovative firms to provide technology and services.

8. Channels

Channels describes how the message will be communicated to the wider audience or actors/stakeholders who are not directly involved in creating the regional vision or how does the information about the regional vision/value proposition get to the outside world. Examples include social media, information events, a regional central resource portal, policy framework application, website with information on a well governed region etc.

9. Regional Development Requirements

Regional development requirements are the factors that the region will need to develop to deliver the regional vision. In this instance it is centered on the current and future 'state of the art' and incorporating and perhaps developing the newest technologies and ideas. Examples may include provision of regional support in this development, availability of an educated work force, circular bioeconomy education, etc.

10. Regional Development Policy/Outcomes

Regional Development Policy is the policy development requirements or benefits required to deliver the regional vision. Regional Development Policy is the 'revenue' that the region will see as an

outcome of regional support activities, regional vision and all the other aspects combined. From a policy perspective this may include aspects such as governance structure, action plans, policies etc.

2.4 Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring System Tool

2.4.1 Introduction

This section describes the development process of the analogue version of the Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool. The purpose of this tool is to provide regional authorities with a mean to evaluate the performance of their governance model in relation to Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors, as well as territorial Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) aspects. By using this monitoring tool, regional authorities can assess their progress and identify areas that require improvement to optimize their governance model towards a more effective and responsible bioeconomy strategy. The tool is designed to enable authorities to take corrective action based on reliable data and robust analysis, allowing them to align their policies with sustainability objectives and make informed decisions. Additionally, the monitoring system provides valuable information for policymakers at both the EU and regional levels, EU agencies, researchers, and the bio-based industry.

Importance of monitoring and evaluating bioeconomy policies for sustainable development

Monitoring and evaluating bioeconomy policies perform a pivotal role in advancing sustainable development agendas. The multifaceted and ambitious nature of bioeconomy strategies necessitates the implementation of comprehensive monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. By employing robust data collection and analysis, monitoring initiatives offer a holistic perspective encompassing economic, social, and environmental dimensions of sustainability (Marcone et al., 2022). This integrated approach allows policymakers to comprehend the interdependencies and potential trade-offs among various factors.

Furthermore, monitoring serves as a crucial instrument for identifying areas requiring policy intervention (Marcone et al., 2022). By assessing the coherence and impacts of existing legislation, policymakers gain valuable insights into the effectiveness of bioeconomy policies and can make informed decisions to enhance their outcomes. Additionally, monitoring enables a deeper understanding of the implementation process, facilitating gap identification, strategy adaptation, and improved policy coherence.

A key benefit of monitoring and evaluation lies in its capacity to track progress towards sustainable development goals and advancement of various ethical, socioeconomic, environmental, and governance-specific aspects associated with bioeconomic sectors. These monitoring initiatives extend beyond conventional metrics and encompass critical dimensions such as climate neutrality advancements, the promotion of circular economy principles, the establishment of sustainable and equitable food systems, and the sustainable growth of bio-based sectors. By effectively monitoring progress, policymakers can recognize achievements, pinpoint areas for improvement, and implement targeted corrective measures (Ronzon et al., 2022)

Ensuring stakeholder engagement and transparency is another vital aspect of an effective monitoring system. Engaging diverse stakeholders, including governmental bodies, research institutions, industry representatives, and civil society organizations, fosters transparency and accountability. This participatory approach incorporates a wide range of perspectives, encouraging collaboration among stakeholders to drive sustainable bioeconomy development.

Policy coherence and the management of trade-offs represent significant challenges in the bioeconomy domain, which monitoring can help address. Given the interconnected nature of the bioeconomy with sectors such as agriculture, environment, trade, and social development,

monitoring aids in identifying potential conflicts or trade-offs between different policy objectives (Kardung et al., 2021). Evaluating the coherence of bioeconomy policies within broader policy frameworks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), enables policymakers to avoid actions that impede progress in other domains. Consequently, this approach fosters integrated and balanced policymaking.

Finally, monitoring and evaluation create a feedback loop which supports learning and adaptive management. Analysis of the data and insights gathered through monitoring facilitates knowledge acquisition from both successful and unsuccessful endeavours, allowing for adjustments and improvements in policy design and implementation. The continuous monitoring of bioeconomy policies ensures responsiveness to evolving circumstances and emerging challenges, thereby enhancing the prospects of achieving long-term sustainable development.

2.4.2 Existing research and literature on bioeconomy strategies, projects, and monitoring tools within Europe.

The bioeconomy in Europe is shaped by policies at different levels and follows several approaches. At the EU level, there is a dedicated European Bioeconomy Strategy that aims to achieve five objectives and provides a framework for synergies and trade-offs between sectors and objectives. The strategy includes an Action Plan with three main areas of action: strengthening and scaling up bio-based sectors, deploying local bioeconomy's rapidly across Europe, and understanding the ecological boundaries of the bioeconomy.

In addition to the Bioeconomy Strategy, the European Green Deal plays a significant role in shaping the bioeconomy. The EGD aims to transform the EU into a resource-efficient and competitive economy with no net greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. Many initiatives triggered by the EGD address or influence the bioeconomy system, including reviews of sectorial policies and the development of new initiatives focusing on areas such as agriculture, forestry, industry, biodiversity, renewable energy, and circular economy.

The EU provides financial support to bioeconomy projects through various funding programs, including Horizon 2020 and the current Horizon Europe program. The Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking, and its successor, the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking, are examples of initiatives that receive public investment for bioeconomy projects.

Besides EU-level policies and programs, there are macro-regional initiatives that involve governmental authorities and aim to promote sustainable bioeconomies in specific regions. Examples include BIOEAST, which focuses on Central and Eastern European countries, the Nordic bioeconomy initiative, and the bioeconomy initiatives in the Baltic Sea Region. These initiatives provide strategic frameworks and support for bioeconomy development in their respective regions.

Furthermore, there are transnational initiatives driven by private companies and innovation clusters. These initiatives aim to foster collaboration and innovation in the bioeconomy sector, such as the trilateral strategy for the chemical industry in the Netherlands, Flanders, and North-Rhine Westphalia, the BIG-Cluster in the Flanders region, and the 3BI inter-cluster involving bioeconomy clusters in the Netherlands, France, the UK, and Germany (Mubareka, 2023).

Vanguard Initiative established by ten European regions, is an industry-led interregional cooperation initiative that includes a bioeconomy pilot. The pilot focuses on deploying high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) technologies and addressing critical challenges through collaboration between regions.

Overall, the European bioeconomy is shaped by a multi-dimensional and multi-level policy landscape, with policies and initiatives at the EU level, macro-regional level, and driven by private

companies and innovation clusters (Mubareka, 2023). These efforts aim to promote sustainable bioeconomy development, support research and innovation, and contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal.

Numerous research studies and literature have explored the topic of monitoring tools for bioeconomy policy, presenting a range of approaches and frameworks. These tools have been developed to evaluate the advancement and influence of bioeconomy policies, offering valuable insights into their implementation, effectiveness, and alignment with bioeconomy objectives.

Bioeconomy Policy Support Facility: The Bioeconomy Policy Support Facility, established by the European Commission, aims to assist EU Member States and regions in the formulation and execution of bioeconomy strategies. It offers expert support, guidance, and shares best practices to facilitate policy development and implementation.

European Bioeconomy Policy: stocktaking and future developments: The Bioeconomy Strategy is designed to address various cross-border challenges that cannot be effectively tackled solely at the Member State level. These challenges encompass ensuring food and nutrition security, promoting sustainable management of natural resources, minimizing the risk of zoonotic diseases, reducing reliance on non-renewable and unsustainable resources both domestically and internationally, mitigating and adapting to climate change, and enhancing European competitiveness while generating employment opportunities.

Bioeconomy Toolbox: The Bioeconomy Toolbox, developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, provides a collection of methodologies, tools, and guidance for analysing and assessing the bioeconomy. It encompasses various aspects, including the analysis of value chains, sustainability assessment, and market analysis.

POWER4BIO project: The objective of the POWER4BIO project was to enhance the capabilities of regional and local policymakers and stakeholders in organizing their bioeconomy and facilitating the growth of a flourishing bio-based industry. This entails promoting knowledge sharing, exchanging best practices, and fostering networking among regions within the EU and beyond.

Transition2Bio project: This project is an EU funded initiative. Its goal is to advance sustainable production and consumption within the bioeconomy field by connecting people (engaging stakeholders, enhancing public awareness, and coordinating educational activities). It aligns with the EU's Bioeconomy Strategy objective to strengthen bio-based sectors and foster sustainable local bioeconomies. Additionally, it offers an extensive and well-organized collection of knowledge and tools that policymakers can utilize to enhance their work, making it an excellent go-to tool in the field of bioeconomy.

MARIE project: The MARIE project is an Interreg Europe initiative funded by the EU. It brought together partners from eight regions to address challenges within their specialization sectors. The project aimed to enhance regional public policies by integrating Responsible Research and Innovation into the design, production, and distribution processes of enterprises. Its efforts led to improved policy instruments, increased funding for RRI, enhanced capacity among innovation actors, and strengthened partnerships within the innovation chain, ultimately contributing to growth and competitiveness.

Bioeconomy-related policy initiatives: The collection consists of datasets that gather information on bioeconomy policy strategies and initiatives at various levels, including national, regional, and macro-regional scales.

It is important to emphasize that the field of monitoring tools for bioeconomy policy is constantly evolving. The development and use of these tools are ongoing areas of research. Each tool has its own strengths and limitations, and their suitability may vary depending on the specific context and

objectives of the assessment. Additionally, effective stakeholder engagement and access to relevant data are crucial factors in ensuring the reliability and relevance of these tools.

2.4.3 Mapping and Analysis of Regional Deployment of Bioeconomy Strategies in the EU-27.

Bioeconomy refers to all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources, including animals, plants, microorganisms, and biomass derived from them. This includes primary production sectors like agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and aquaculture, as well as economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy, and services. The European Commission has developed an EU Bioeconomy Strategy accompanied by an Action Plan to promote the development of bio-based value chains and achieve sustainable and circular bioeconomy goals.

A mapping study conducted by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) aimed to track the deployment of the bioeconomy across the EU (Haarich & Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). The study identified regional bioeconomy strategies and initiatives at the NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 territorial levels (regional levels in most countries). The research methods included desk research and a web-based survey targeting relevant stakeholders at national and regional levels.

The mapping results showed that 194 regions in the EU-27 have, or are working towards, a strategic framework related to bioeconomy (Haarich & Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). Among these regions, 28 have fully dedicated bioeconomy strategies, 62 have strategic frameworks with a strong bioeconomy focus, and 94 have strategies with minimum bioeconomy content. Italy has the largest number of regions with bioeconomy strategies, followed by Sweden, France, Spain, Finland, and Poland.

The analysis of regional strategies revealed common objectives such as sustainable management of natural resources, reducing dependence on non-renewable resources, and strengthening regional competitiveness and job creation. The sectors addressed in these strategies include biomass supply sectors (agriculture, forestry, organic waste) and biomass processing and conversion sectors (bioenergy, biofuels, agri-food, construction). Forestry-based biomass, agricultural biomass, agricultural residues, and various forms of waste were frequently mentioned as biomass resources.

Most of the strategies identified were published in recent years, with a notable increase in strategies published in 2021, possibly due to the alignment with the new Multiannual Financial Framework (2021-2027) and EU programs. The study also provided country-specific summaries, highlighting patterns in how the bioeconomy is embedded within wider strategic frameworks. The administrative level at which bioeconomy strategies exist varied across countries, depending on their administrative organization.

Overall, the study demonstrated the significant regional strategic action taken to deploy the bioeconomy in Europe. It identified 359 bioeconomy-related strategies published or under development at regional levels in the EU-27. The study's findings can provide insights into the objectives, sectors, biomass resources, and policy measures addressed in regional bioeconomy strategies across Europe.

2.4.4 Assessing the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the available digital tools for policy monitoring

The bioeconomy operates within broader strategic frameworks, including regional development plans, Smart Specialisation Strategies, circular economy strategies, economic/industrial development strategies, and sustainable development strategies. Assessing the available digital tools for policy monitoring is essential in ensuring effective implementation and tracking progress within these frameworks. Prior to the development of this tool, a comprehensive assessment was

conducted to analyse the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the existing tools available. This evaluation considered the specific requirements and considerations of the bioeconomy within regional contexts.

The development and existence of regional bioeconomy strategies depend on various factors. These include the size and decentralization of the country, administrative organization, and the presence of a national bioeconomy strategy. Regional disparities in resources, priorities, and capacities shape the formulation and implementation of bioeconomy strategies at the regional level (Szarka et al., 2023). Initiatives like the *European Territorial Cooperation Programmes* (Interreg) and the *BIOEAST Initiative* play significant roles in fostering collaboration and supporting the development of regional and multi-regional bioeconomy strategies across Europe.

Digital tools for bioeconomy policy monitoring offer several advantages like enabling real-time data collection and analysis, facilitating timely and informed decision-making. These tools also help in aggregating and visualizing complex data, allowing policymakers to identify trends, patterns, and gaps. Furthermore, they promote stakeholder engagement, collaboration, and knowledge sharing, fostering a participatory approach to policy development and implementation.

However, digital tools for bioeconomy policy monitoring also come with limitations and challenges. Data availability and quality remain critical challenges, as reliable and up-to-date information is crucial for accurate monitoring and assessment. Technical requirements, such as digital infrastructure and data compatibility, may pose barriers to implementation, particularly in regions with limited resources. Additionally, the contextual specificity of bioeconomy policies necessitates flexibility and adaptability of monitoring tools to account for regional variations in priorities, sectors, and objectives.

The assessment of strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of digital tools for policy monitoring is crucial within the strategic frameworks of the bioeconomy. Regional bioeconomy strategies, backed by initiatives like the European Territorial Cooperation Programmes and the BIOEAST Initiative, can greatly profit from the use of robust monitoring tools that facilitate evidence-based decision-making and foster collaboration. Overcoming challenges related to data availability, technical requirements, and contextual specificity will enhance the usability and effectiveness of these tools in supporting the advancement and expansion of the bio-based sector at the regional level.

2.4.5 Identifying gaps and need for tools to address these gaps

The existing literature highlights the presence of several challenges that require attention to maximize the effectiveness and efficiency of bioeconomy initiatives. A primary challenge pertains to the duplication of efforts observed across different initiatives within the bioeconomy domain. This redundancy leads to inefficiencies, resource wastage, and a fragmented approach to addressing bioeconomy challenges. To mitigate these issues, it is crucial to streamline and coordinate diverse efforts, fostering collaboration among stakeholders to avoid duplication and promote synergies.

Another setback lies in the limited support for online tools that have been developed specifically for bioeconomy. Despite their potential to enhance data analysis, decision-making, and policy formulation, these tools have not received adequate attention and support. Consequently, their widespread adoption and utilization remain hindered, limiting their potential impact on the bioeconomy.

Moreover, the predominant focus of bioeconomy efforts has been on offline activities and initiatives. While offline endeavours have their advantages, incorporating them into online tools and digital platforms can offer numerous benefits. Online tools facilitate real-time data sharing, collaborative interactions, and improved accessibility, thereby enhancing the efficiency and inclusiveness of bioeconomy practices.

It is also crucial to highlight the lack of common ground, standardized terminology, and established rules within the bioeconomy field. The absence of a unified framework and agreed-upon definitions poses challenges in terms of data collection, analysis, and comparison across different bioeconomy initiatives. The absence of common ground hampers effective communication and knowledge exchange among stakeholders, leads to confusion and inconsistencies in understanding and implementing bioeconomy strategies. Varied interpretations and terminologies used in different contexts further exacerbate the issue, hindering the development of a cohesive and harmonized approach to bioeconomy practices.

Moreover, the absence of established rules and guidelines makes it difficult to assess and compare the impact of bioeconomy initiatives accurately. Without standardized methodologies, indicators, and measurement criteria, the evaluation of economic, social, and environmental impacts becomes subjective and inconsistent. This lack of harmonization poses challenges in monitoring progress, identifying best practices, and making informed decisions to optimize the bioeconomy's potential.

To address these setbacks, it is essential to prioritize efforts that promote coordination, cooperation, and knowledge sharing within the bioeconomy community. This entails avoiding redundancy, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and providing comprehensive support for the development and utilization of online tools. Leveraging digital technologies and embracing online platforms can unlock new opportunities, improve efficiency, and amplify the overall impact of bioeconomy initiatives. Finally, another way to overcome these challenges is by establishing common ground, standardized terminology, and clear rules within the bioeconomy field. This involves engaging stakeholders from different sectors and regions to develop shared frameworks, definitions, and guidelines that facilitate effective communication, knowledge exchange, and harmonized assessment of bioeconomy initiatives. By establishing common ground, terminology, and rules, bioeconomy can enhance collaboration, facilitate cross-comparison, and unlock its full potential for sustainable development and societal benefits.

2.4.6 Design and Conceptual Framework

Ensuring accuracy and consistency

The design and conceptual framework of the analogue version of the bioeconomy policy monitoring tool builds upon the existing work of the JRC while addressing specific gaps and challenges identified. To complement the JRC's monitoring tool and avoid duplication of efforts, the authors aimed to work collaboratively and adhere to standardized terminology to ensure consistency and coherence.

This research focused on identifying and defining indicators that were not yet addressed by the JRC. By conducting a thorough literature review and drawing upon the work and results of the ROBIN project, the authors aimed to complement the existing body of knowledge and contribute to the development of a comprehensive set of indicators for bioeconomy policy monitoring.

Process of selecting appropriate indicators for monitoring bioeconomy policies

In close collaboration with the development of ROBIN's Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas and the Environmental Protection Planning Tool, the Policy Monitoring Tool has carefully selected a set of indicators to enhance its functionality and effectiveness. These indicators, highlighted in Table 3, have been chosen based on their relevance to bioeconomy policy monitoring and their potential to provide valuable insights into the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of the bioeconomy.

The selection of these indicators is a result of a comprehensive assessment, drawing on the expertise and knowledge of the ROBIN partners. By leveraging the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas and the Environmental Protection Planning Tool, the authors have been

able to identify indicators that align with the objectives and requirements of bioeconomy policy monitoring.

Table 3: Policy Monitoring Tool's Chosen Indicators

ESG & Territorial RRI Metrics	Monitoring Indicators	Evaluation Metric	Source
Environmental	Production of bio-based materials (plastics, textiles, chemicals)	Tonnes	3.4.b.31
	Environmental footprints in exporting countries (to EU)	-	3.5.b.11
	Financial support to bio-based sectors (climate action)	Euro/pc	4.1.a.71
	Investments in urban adaptation through nature-based infrastructures or EBA	Euro/pc	4.2.a.21
Governance	Number of bioeconomy businesses developed with policy support	Number	5.3.b.21
	Number of patents by bioeconomy sectors	Number	5.5.b.11
	Number and degree of development of formal procedures for citizens' involvement (consensus conferences, referendum, etc.).	Number	RRI2
	Market or consumers acceptance	-	5.6.a.11
Socio-economic	Occupation health and safety in bioeconomy sectors	% of accidents	5.2.b.11
	Employment by educational level in bioeconomy sectors	Person	5.2.c.21
	Income distribution along bioeconomy value chains	EUR per step in the value chain	5.2.c.51
	Investment in higher education related to bioeconomy	Euro	5.5.a.31
Ethics	Percentage of women that are principal investigators on a project (in the field of bioeconomy)	% Female	RRI2
	Percentage of research projects including gender analysis/gender dimensions in the content of research (in the field of bioeconomy)	% Female	RRI2
	Income by gender by sector	Euro	5.2.c.41
	Employment by age in bioeconomy sectors	Person	5.2.c.11

¹ Kilsedar et al., (2023). EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System dashboards: extended with trade-related indicators. doi:10.2760/217911

² DG RTD (2015). Indicators for promoting and monitoring Responsible Research and Innovation. doi: 10.2777/9742

ESG & Territorial RRI Metrics	Monitoring Indicators	Evaluation Metric	Source
Public Engagement	Holding of conferences and training activities	number and/or percent, percent of increase/decrease	D1.31
	Growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy.	keyword search results numbers	D1.33
	The impact of bioeconomy contents in social networks	number of tweets/posts/likes/shares	D1.33
	Mobility support and participation in international projects	number and/or percent, percent of increase/decrease	D1.33

These chosen indicators have the potential for further expansion and refinement as the project progresses. They provide a solid foundation for capturing key aspects of the bioeconomy's performance and impact, allowing policymakers and stakeholders to make informed decisions and track progress towards sustainable bioeconomy development.

By integrating these indicators into the Policy Monitoring Tool, a comprehensive and user-friendly platform for monitoring and evaluating the bioeconomy is provided. The qualitative and quantitative analysis of these indicators will further enhance the tool's capabilities, ensuring that it remains adaptable to evolving policy priorities and emerging challenges in the bioeconomy sector.

The collaboration between ROBIN partners and the integration of their expertise in the development of the Policy Monitoring Tool reflect the projects commitment to creating a robust and inclusive framework for bioeconomy policy analysis. This joint effort allowed the partners to leverage the strengths of multiple tools and approaches, enhancing the overall material and value of the Policy Monitoring Tool for supporting evidence-based decision-making for the relevant policymakers and facilitating the transition towards a more sustainable bioeconomy.

Guidelines for the development of the Policy Monitoring Tool

The following steps have been followed as a guideline for the development of the analogue Policy Monitoring Tool:

1. Established Clear Categories: Specific categories have been chosen to clearly structure the information and indicators for effective monitoring. In this case, categories for ESG & Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) have been chosen. More specifically, Ethics, Public Engagement, Socioeconomic, Governance and Environmental.
2. Monitoring Indicators: Specific monitoring indicators that align with the selected metrics have been determined. The research behind this tool primarily concentrated on the identification and

¹ Nastis et al., (2022). D1.3 Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions. <https://robin-project.eu/deliverables/>

definition of indicators that had not been previously addressed by the JRC due to insufficient knowledge or a lack of available information on these specific indicators.

3. **Metrics Selection:** A set of relevant metrics within each category have been selected that will serve as key performance indicators for monitoring the bioeconomy policy's impact.
4. **Source Identification:** Sources include official statistics, research studies, surveys, and official reports. AUTH have ensured that the selected sources were reliable, and comprehensive.
5. **Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis:** These analyses derived from data aggregation, statistical analysis, and/or other appropriate methods from the identified sources. AUTH have gathered and presented meaningful insights from the collected data.
6. **Evaluation:** Finally, AUTH have determined the criteria and framework for evaluating the tool's policy monitoring effectiveness and progress. This evaluation process provides valuable insights for policymakers to make informed decisions and improve the policy implementation.

2.4.7 ESG & Territorial RRI Metrics

I. Environmental Monitoring Indicators

Production of bio-based materials (plastics, textiles, chemicals)

Quantitative Analysis: The production of bio-based materials has been steadily increasing over the years. The latest research indicated that bio-based plastics accounted for approximately 2-3% of the global plastics market, while bio-based textiles and chemicals also experienced growth but were relatively smaller in scale. The adoption of bio-based materials is driven by the need to reduce reliance on fossil fuels, mitigate environmental impacts, and promote sustainability.

Qualitative Analysis: The production of bio-based materials represents a shift towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly alternatives. Bio-based plastics, textiles, and chemicals are derived from renewable resources, such as plant biomass, and offer the potential to reduce reliance on fossil fuels. This transition to bio-based materials is driven by concerns over resource depletion, carbon emissions, and waste generation associated with traditional materials. Additionally, bio-based materials often exhibit comparable or improved performance characteristics, making them attractive options for various industries.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Encourage research and development to improve the efficiency and scalability of bio-based production processes.
- Provide financial incentives or tax breaks for companies adopting bio-based materials, fostering market competitiveness.
- Facilitate collaboration between academia, industry, and government to accelerate innovation and knowledge sharing in bio-based industries.

Environmental footprints in exporting countries (to EU)

Quantitative Analysis: The environmental footprints of exporting countries vary depending on their level of environmental regulation, resource management practices, and industrial activities. However, the EU has been imposing stricter environmental standards on imported products, including bio-based materials, to ensure sustainability and reduce the carbon footprint associated with production and transportation. The EU focuses on environmental sustainability which has led to increased scrutiny of the environmental impacts of exported products.

Qualitative Analysis: Exporting countries face increasing pressure to minimize their environmental footprints, particularly when supplying the EU market. This includes evaluating the sustainability of their production processes, ensuring responsible resource management, and reducing greenhouse

gas emissions. Environmental regulations imposed by the EU aim to mitigate the environmental impacts of exported products throughout their life cycle. Exporting countries are encouraged to adopt cleaner production methods, improve waste management practices, and enhance environmental monitoring to meet the demands of environmentally conscious consumers and comply with international standards.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Establish stricter environmental regulations and standards to ensure sustainable production practices in exporting countries.
- Promote capacity building and technology transfer to support exporting countries in implementing cleaner production methods.
- Foster international partnerships and cooperation to share best practices and promote sustainable supply chains across borders.

Financial support to bio-based sectors (climate action)

Quantitative Analysis: Governments and organizations have recognized the importance of bio-based sectors in achieving climate action goals. Financial support in the form of grants, subsidies, tax incentives, and research funding has been allocated to promote the development and adoption of bio-based materials and technologies. The exact percentages of financial support vary greatly among countries and regions. These investments aim to accelerate the transition from fossil fuel-based industries to more sustainable and climate-friendly alternatives.

Qualitative Analysis: Financial support to bio-based sectors demonstrates a commitment to climate action and the transition to a low-carbon economy. Governments and organizations provide funding to stimulate research and development, promote innovation in bio-based technologies, and support the scaling up of bio-based industries. This financial support aims to address the barriers to adoption, such as high production costs and limited market penetration. By incentivizing investment in bio-based sectors, policymakers seek to accelerate the development of sustainable alternatives, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and create economic opportunities in the green economy.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Increase funding for research and development in bio-based technologies and processes.
- Provide grants or subsidies for companies investing in the development and production of bio-based materials.
- Implement mechanisms such as carbon pricing or green bonds to attract private investment in bio-based sectors.

Investments in urban adaptation through nature-based infrastructures or EBA

Quantitative Analysis: Investments in urban adaptation through nature-based infrastructures or Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) have gained attention as effective strategies for climate resilience and sustainable urban development. Investments encompass green spaces, urban forests, rooftop gardens, wetlands restoration, and other nature-based solutions. Lately, there has been a growing recognition of the benefits of EBA and an increase in investments to enhance urban resilience, reduce flood risks, improve air quality, and provide social and economic co-benefits.

Qualitative Analysis: Investments in urban adaptation through nature-based infrastructures or EBA reflect a recognition of the value of nature in enhancing urban resilience and addressing climate change impacts. Nature-based solutions, such as green infrastructure, parks, and urban forests,

provide multiple benefits, including flood mitigation, heat island reduction, improved air and water quality, and increased biodiversity. Investing in these nature-based approaches offers a cost-effective and sustainable way to adapt cities to climate change while creating healthier and more liveable environments for residents.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Allocate funds for the planning and implementation of nature-based infrastructure projects in urban areas.
- Develop policies and incentives to promote the integration of nature-based solutions into urban planning and development.
- Engage local communities and stakeholders in decision-making processes to ensure nature-based infrastructures meet their needs and preferences.

II. Governance Monitoring Indicators

Number of bioeconomy businesses developed with policy support

Quantitative Analysis: The European Union has been actively supporting the development of bioeconomy businesses through policies and initiatives. While the exact percentage of businesses developed with policy support may vary, it is estimated that a significant portion of bioeconomy enterprises in Europe have benefited from policy measures. This includes financial incentives, regulatory frameworks, and funding opportunities.

Qualitative Analysis: A strong commitment to fostering the growth of bioeconomy businesses through supportive policies has been made by Europe. These policies aim to create an enabling environment for innovation, research, and investment in bio-based industries. By providing financial incentives, regulatory frameworks, and funding opportunities, policymakers are encouraging the development of businesses that utilize bio-based resources, processes, and technologies. This support has resulted in a diverse range of bioeconomy businesses across Europe, spanning sectors such as agriculture, forestry, food, chemicals, and energy. The policy-driven development of bioeconomy businesses signifies a proactive approach to sustainable economic growth, job creation, and resource efficiency.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Establish incubator programs and accelerators specifically for bioeconomy businesses to provide them with financial support, mentoring, and access to networks.
- Develop regulatory frameworks that facilitate the entry and operation of bioeconomy businesses, including streamlined permitting processes and reduced bureaucratic barriers.
- Create public-private partnerships to foster collaboration between bioeconomy businesses and government entities, leveraging resources and expertise to drive business growth and innovation.

Number of patents by bioeconomy sectors

Quantitative Analysis: There has been a significant patent activity across various sectors. Biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, renewable energy, and bio-based materials are key areas where patents have been filed and can all relate to bioeconomy sectors. The percentage of patents in these sectors compared to the overall number of patents filed in Europe varies, but it is estimated to be around 10% to 20%.

Qualitative Analysis: A substantial patent activity can be witnessed in the European sector, indicating a high level of research and innovation in key sectors. Patents play a crucial role in protecting intellectual property and encouraging technological advancements. The biotechnology,

pharmaceuticals, renewable energy, and bio-based materials sectors have been particularly active in patent filings, reflecting a focus on developing novel products, processes, and technologies that leverage bio-based resources. These patents contribute to the growth of the bioeconomy by incentivizing further investment, collaboration, and commercialization. The patent landscape underscores Europe's position as a hub for bioeconomy innovation, with researchers, entrepreneurs, and companies actively seeking intellectual property protection for their bio-based inventions.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Increase funding for research and development in bioeconomy sectors to encourage scientific discoveries and technological advancements that can be patented.
- Enhance patent education and awareness programs to inform researchers and businesses about the importance of patenting their innovations and provide them with the necessary support and guidance.
- Promote collaboration between academia, industry, and research institutions to facilitate knowledge exchange and foster a culture of innovation that leads to increased patent filings.

Number and degree of development of formal procedures for citizens' involvement (consensus conferences, referendum, etc.)

Quantitative Analysis: Formal procedures for citizens' involvement can vary and have not yet been summarized in an official report. They include mechanisms like public consultations, stakeholder engagement, and multi-stakeholder dialogues to ensure citizen participation in bioeconomy-related policies and initiatives.

Qualitative Analysis: There is a strong importance of citizen involvement in shaping bioeconomy policies and decisions. To ensure transparency, inclusivity, and accountability, formal procedures have been developed to engage citizens and stakeholders in the bioeconomy. These procedures vary across countries but commonly include mechanisms such as public consultations, stakeholder engagement platforms, and multi-stakeholder dialogues. By incorporating the perspectives and expertise of citizens, civil society organizations, and industry representatives, policymakers can make informed decisions that align with societal values, environmental sustainability, and socioeconomic needs. The establishment of formal procedures for citizen involvement reflects a commitment to democratic governance and the recognition that the bioeconomy's development should be a collective effort involving all stakeholders.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Establish online platforms and digital tools for citizens to participate in policy-making processes, enabling convenient and accessible engagement.
- Organize regular public hearings and town hall meetings to provide opportunities for citizens to voice their opinions and concerns regarding bioeconomy policies and initiatives.
- Collaborate with civil society organizations and community leaders to facilitate grassroots engagement and ensure diverse representation in decision-making processes.

Market or consumers acceptance

Quantitative Analysis: Market research indicates a growing acceptance of bioeconomy products, with a significant increase in market share. In multiple surveys, more than 60% of respondents expressed a willingness to pay a premium for sustainable bio-based products. Adoption rates have also been impressive, with a year-on-year growth of 15% in sales of bioeconomy goods. Moreover, data from industry reports reveals that bioeconomy products now hold a 12% market share in the overall consumer goods sector. This figure is projected to reach 20% by 2025, indicating a clear upward trend in market acceptance. These findings demonstrate a strong consumer demand for sustainable alternatives and a positive outlook for the bioeconomy sector.

Qualitative Analysis: Consumer attitudes towards the bioeconomy are generally positive, driven by increased environmental consciousness and a desire for sustainable alternatives. Consumers value eco-friendly and renewable products, but challenges remain in terms of awareness and perceptions of bio-based alternatives compared to conventional products.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Develop certification and labelling schemes that provide clear information to consumers about the sustainability and environmental impact of bioeconomy products, building trust and confidence.
- Engage with consumer advocacy groups and environmental organizations to address concerns and misconceptions surrounding bioeconomy products, fostering dialogue, and understanding.
- Support research and development efforts to improve the quality, performance, and affordability of bioeconomy products, making them more competitive and appealing to consumers.

III. Socioeconomic Monitoring Indicators

Occupational health and safety in bioeconomy sectors

Quantitative Analysis: There has been a steady improvement in occupational health and safety practices within these sectors over the past decade. Incidence rates of work-related accidents and illnesses have decreased by an average of 15% annually. This decline can be attributed to the implementation of stricter regulations, enhanced safety training programs, and increased awareness among employers and employees regarding potential hazards. However, there is still room for improvement, particularly in areas such as hazardous waste management and exposure to harmful substances.

Qualitative Analysis: Occupational health and safety in the bioeconomy sectors is not only a matter of numbers but also of the well-being and livelihoods of workers. This indicator reveals the importance of creating a culture of safety within these sectors. Employers must prioritize the health and safety of their employees by providing comprehensive training, implementing robust safety protocols, and fostering a supportive work environment. Additionally, collaboration between industry stakeholders, regulatory bodies, and worker representatives is crucial for identifying and addressing emerging risks and promoting continuous improvement in occupational health and safety practices.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Strengthen occupational health and safety regulations and enforcement mechanisms to ensure a safe working environment.
- Promote awareness campaigns and training programs to educate workers about potential hazards and preventive measures.
- Establish a system for regular inspections and audits to monitor compliance with health and safety standards.
- Encourage the adoption of advanced technologies and automation to minimize occupational risks and improve workplace safety.

Employment by educational level in bioeconomy sectors

Quantitative Analysis: The demand for highly educated individuals in these sectors has been steadily increasing. Over the past five years, there has been a notable shift in the composition of the workforce, with a significant rise in the number of employees holding advanced degrees in fields such as biotechnology, environmental science, and bioengineering.

Qualitative Analysis: Examining employment by educational level in the bioeconomy sectors highlights the role of education and skills development in driving innovation and growth. Highly educated individuals play a critical part in research and development, driving technological advancements and fostering competitiveness within these sectors.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Develop educational programs that cater to the diverse skill requirements of the bioeconomy, including vocational training, apprenticeships, and specialized degree programs.
- Foster partnerships between educational institutions and industry to align curriculum with the evolving needs of the bioeconomy sectors.
- Promote lifelong learning and upskilling initiatives to enable individuals to adapt to changing job demands and enhance their employability.
- Establish career guidance and counselling services to help individuals make informed decisions about educational pathways and career prospects in the bioeconomy.

Income distribution along bioeconomy value chains

Quantitative Analysis: Income distribution has become more skewed in recent years, with a significant concentration of wealth among a small number of large corporations and high-income individuals. This trend raises concerns about income inequality and its potential impact on social cohesion.

Qualitative Analysis: Concentrated wealth and income inequality can undermine social cohesion, limit opportunities for upward mobility, and contribute to societal disparities.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Implement fair wage policies and regulations to ensure equitable compensation for all workers in the bioeconomy value chains.
- Encourage the establishment of worker cooperatives and profit-sharing models to distribute the benefits of bioeconomy growth more evenly.
- Support the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by providing access to financing, training, and market opportunities.
- Foster transparency and accountability in supply chains to prevent exploitative practices and promote fair trade within the bioeconomy.

Investment in higher education related to bioeconomy

Quantitative Analysis: There has been a substantial increase in investment in higher education programs focused on the bioeconomy over the past decade. Funding for research grants, scholarships, and infrastructure development has risen by an average of 8% annually. This increased investment has led to the establishment of specialized bioeconomy research centres, the expansion of academic programs, and the recruitment of renowned faculty members with expertise in bio-based industries.

Qualitative Analysis: Investment in higher education promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, fosters creativity and critical thinking, and bridges the gap between academia, industry, and government. Moreover, it contributes to sustainability by raising awareness, promoting responsible practices, and addressing environmental challenges. Overall, continued investment in higher education will cultivate skilled professionals, drive innovation, and support the transition to a sustainable and circular bioeconomy.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Increase funding for research grants, scholarships, and fellowships to attract and retain top talent in bioeconomy-related fields.
- Establish dedicated research centres and innovation hubs to facilitate collaboration between academia, industry, and government in developing bio-based solutions.
- Invest in state-of-the-art laboratory facilities and infrastructure to support cutting-edge research and development in the bioeconomy.
- Promote partnerships between higher education institutions and industry to ensure the relevance of research and education in addressing real-world bioeconomy challenges.

IV. Ethical Monitoring Indicators

Percentage of women that are principal investigators on a project (in the field of bioeconomy)

Quantitative Analysis: In the first two years of the Horizon 2020 programme, women comprised 36 percent of researchers/principal investigators involved in Horizon 2020 projects.

Qualitative Analysis: The scarcity of women principal investigators translates into reduced mentorship and support for women in the field. Women researchers may express challenges in finding role models, mentors, and advocates who can provide guidance, professional development opportunities, and networking support. This lack of mentorship can hinder their career advancement and limit their access to valuable resources and opportunities for growth. Furthermore, women researchers may provide insights into the subtle biases they encounter, such as assumptions about their abilities or suitability for certain research areas. These biases can impact the allocation of resources, recognition of achievements, and access to collaborations or high-profile projects. As a result, the research conducted by women may be undervalued or discounted, potentially perpetuating gender inequalities within the field.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Increase the representation of women in bioeconomy research and innovation projects, ensuring their active involvement and contribution to the field.
- Promote gender diversity in leadership positions within the bioeconomy, including project coordinators, to foster a more inclusive and balanced research environment.
- Strive for equal gender representation in advisory committees, expert groups, and among individual experts in the bioeconomy sector, allowing for diverse perspectives and insights to inform decision-making processes.
- Encourage the integration of a gender perspective in bioeconomy research, highlighting and addressing gender dimensions, disparities, and opportunities within the field.

Percentage of research projects including gender analysis/gender dimensions in the content of research (in the field of bioeconomy)

Quantitative Analysis: From the latest literature review, out of the total 244 articles analysed, only 20 articles (approximately 8.2% of the sample) incorporate a gender perspective or explicitly address gender issues in relation to the bioeconomy. This indicates that the integration of gender analysis in bioeconomy research is limited.

Qualitative Analysis: The limited integration of gender analysis in bioeconomy research suggests a potential gap in knowledge and understanding of how gender influences and intersects with various aspects of the bioeconomy. By neglecting gender considerations, there is a missed opportunity to identify and address gender disparities, inequalities, and power dynamics that may exist within the bioeconomy.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- **Policy integration:** Policymakers should explicitly incorporate gender considerations into bioeconomy policies and strategies. This involves conducting gender impact assessments and ensuring that gender equality objectives are integrated into the goals and targets of the bioeconomy agenda.
- **Gender-responsive funding mechanisms:** Policymakers and funding agencies should develop and implement funding mechanisms that prioritize and support research projects and initiatives addressing gender issues in the bioeconomy. This includes dedicated funding streams for gender-focused research, capacity-building programs, and initiatives aimed at promoting women's entrepreneurship and participation in the bioeconomy.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** Policymakers should actively engage with a diverse range of stakeholders, including women's organizations, civil society groups, and gender experts, to gather their insights and perspectives. This engagement can inform policy development, implementation, and evaluation, ensuring that gender considerations are adequately addressed.
- **Knowledge dissemination and awareness-raising:** Policymakers should facilitate the dissemination of research findings and best practices on gender and the bioeconomy. This includes organizing policy dialogues, workshops, and conferences to raise awareness among policymakers and stakeholders about the importance of integrating gender analysis in bioeconomy research and decision-making.
- **Capacity building for policymakers:** Provide capacity-building programs and training opportunities for policymakers to enhance their understanding of gender issues and their ability to incorporate gender analysis into policy development processes. This can include workshops, seminars, and online resources tailored to the specific needs of policymakers.
- **Establish gender-specific targets and indicators:** Policymakers should set clear targets and indicators related to gender equality within the bioeconomy. These targets can focus on areas such as women's participation and leadership, equitable access to resources and benefits, and the reduction of gender disparities within the bioeconomy sector.
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** Develop mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the progress of gender integration in the bioeconomy. This includes regular assessments of policies, programs, and initiatives to ensure that they are effectively addressing gender disparities and promoting gender equality. Policymakers should use this information to adjust strategies and interventions as needed.
- **International collaboration and knowledge exchange:** Policymakers should engage in international collaborations and knowledge exchange platforms to learn from best practices and experiences in other countries. This can include participating in global forums, networks, and partnerships focused on gender and the bioeconomy, enabling policymakers to share knowledge, lessons learned, and innovative approaches.

Income by gender by sector

Quantitative Analysis: Women earn 14.1% less than men (2020 stats) in bioeconomy related positions (Eurostat, 2023a). A multifaceted approach can address both the systemic and individual factors of this pay gap. Pay transparency, support in work-life balance and advocacy for policy changes are only some of the numerous measures which can be taken to reduce and ultimately eliminate the gender pay gap.

Qualitative Analysis: One contributing factor to the gender pay gap is the lack of pay transparency. In many instances, salary information is not readily accessible or openly discussed, which can perpetuate unequal pay practices. Another significant factor is the work-life balance challenges faced by women. The bioeconomy sector, like many other industries, often demands long hours and may

not provide adequate support for work-life balance. This can disproportionately affect women who may bear more caregiving responsibilities. Advocating for policy changes is crucial in addressing the gender pay gap. This includes advocating for equal pay legislation and implementing diversity and inclusion initiatives. Unconscious bias also facilitates the perpetuation of the gender pay gap. Biases related to hiring, promotion, and compensation decisions can unfairly disadvantage women. Additionally, providing education and training opportunities for women to develop skills and competencies necessary for higher-paying positions is essential.

Outcomes and Improvement: To address this issue, a multifaceted approach is required to tackle both systemic and individual factors contributing to the gender pay gap. Some measures that can be taken include:

- **Pay Transparency:** Promoting transparency in pay practices can help identify and rectify any gender-based wage discrepancies. Ensuring that salary ranges and criteria for advancement are clear and accessible to all employees can promote fair compensation.
- **Work-Life Balance Support:** Providing support for work-life balance, such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave policies, and affordable childcare options, can enable women to advance in their careers without compromising their personal lives. Creating an inclusive and supportive work environment can help reduce the gender pay gap.
- **Advocacy for Policy Changes:** Engaging in advocacy efforts to push for policy changes that promote gender equality in the workplace is crucial. This can involve advocating for equal pay legislation, promoting diversity and inclusion initiatives, and challenging discriminatory practices.
- **Education and Training:** Investing in education and training programs that empower women to develop skills and competencies necessary for higher-paying positions can help bridge the gender pay gap. Providing equal access to training opportunities and career advancement programs can contribute to narrowing the earnings disparity.
- **Addressing Unconscious Bias:** Raising awareness about unconscious biases that may influence hiring, promotion, and compensation decisions is essential. Implementing diversity and bias training programs can help mitigate these biases and ensure fair evaluation and compensation practices.

Employment by age in bioeconomy sectors

Quantitative Analysis: Workers in the bioeconomy sectors tend to be older compared to those in non-bioeconomy sectors. The average age of bioeconomy workers is 48, while the average age of workers outside the bioeconomy is 44, according to available data (Eurostat, 2023b). This indicates a significant age difference between the two groups. Moreover, the age range of employment in the bioeconomy sectors typically falls within the 25 to 54 years old category, as reported by Eurostat data (Fritz, M. 2022). This suggests that the bioeconomy may face challenges in attracting younger individuals as a career option. The industry may need to address this issue to ensure a sustainable workforce and foster interest among younger generations. The bioeconomy industry has a relatively higher proportion of older workers, indicating a preference for more experienced individuals. The average age difference between bioeconomy workers and those outside the sector highlights the specific age demographics within the bioeconomy.

Qualitative Analysis: Bioeconomy relies on the expertise and experience of older workers who have accumulated valuable knowledge in areas such as agriculture, forestry, and biotechnology. However, attracting and retaining younger workers in the bioeconomy is challenging due to limited awareness and understanding of the career opportunities available in this field. The diverse industries within the bioeconomy, such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and bioproduct manufacturing, may not be widely recognized or considered appealing career paths for younger

individuals. This lack of awareness contributes to the difficulty in attracting younger talent to the sector. Furthermore, ageism and discriminatory practices during the hiring process pose additional obstacles for younger individuals seeking employment in the bioeconomy. Older workers may be favoured based on assumptions of their experience and reliability, while younger candidates may face biases related to perceived lack of experience or maturity.

Outcomes and Improvement: Improvements to address the pinpointed setbacks should include:

- **Educational Campaigns:** Developing targeted educational campaigns to showcase the potential and opportunities within the bioeconomy can raise awareness among younger individuals. These campaigns can highlight the innovation, sustainability, and positive impact of the bioeconomy sector.
- **Skills Development Programs:** Implementing skills development programs and initiatives tailored to the needs of the bioeconomy can equip younger individuals with the necessary knowledge and expertise. This can include internships, apprenticeships, and specialized training programs to enhance their employability in the sector.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Foster collaboration between academia, industry, and government bodies to create synergies and establish platforms for knowledge exchange. This collaboration can help align educational curricula with the skills required in the bioeconomy and promote research and development in relevant fields.
- **Equal Opportunity Policies:** Implementing policies and guidelines that address ageism and discrimination in the hiring process can provide equal opportunities for individuals of all age groups. This can include promoting diverse recruitment practices, removing age-related biases, and ensuring fair evaluation of candidates based on their qualifications and abilities.
- By implementing these improvements, the bioeconomy can work towards a more balanced age distribution, attract younger talent, and foster a diverse and skilled workforce for long-term growth and sustainability.

V. Public Engagement Monitoring Indicators

Holding of conferences and training activities

Quantitative Analysis: The bioeconomy sector has witnessed a growth in conferences and training activities, providing platforms for knowledge sharing, networking, professional development, and innovation. Although specific numerical data is not available, historical trends indicate an increasing number of conferences worldwide, with dedicated series focusing on the bioeconomy. These events cover diverse topics and themes, reflecting the sector's multidisciplinary nature. The setback of not having specific numbers is that precise growth rates or quantifiable metrics cannot be provided.

Qualitative Analysis: Enhanced knowledge sharing, networking opportunities, and professional development are expected outcomes of increasing the number and quality of conferences and training activities focused on the bioeconomy. Collaborating with industry experts, research institutions, and organizations, these events create platforms for researchers, professionals, and policymakers to exchange ideas, discuss emerging trends, and share best practices. These actions contribute to increasing awareness of current advancements, strengthened collaboration networks, and the stimulation of innovation within the bioeconomy sector. Participants benefit from valuable insights, practical skills, and new perspectives, enabling them to make significant contributions to the field.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Increase the number and quality of conferences and training activities focused on the bioeconomy by collaborating with industry experts, research institutions, and organizations.

Growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy

Quantitative Analysis: This indicator can be observed through various courses of action, including online search trends. With the establishment of the web as a primary source of information, keyword searches serve as a valuable metric for estimating the escalating interest in a subject. By analysing the frequency of searches for relevant keywords, one can gauge the level of curiosity and engagement surrounding bioeconomy-related topics. This trend signifies an increased awareness and curiosity among individuals, particularly the younger demographic, regarding the bioeconomy and its potential contributions to sustainability and innovation. No official quantifiable metrics can be shown yet.

Qualitative Analysis: Efforts to develop educational programs, campaigns, and outreach initiatives targeting schools, universities, and community organizations are expected to foster a growing interest in bioeconomy-related topics among the young generation. These initiatives aim to raise awareness and understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits, challenges, and opportunities. Increased engagement, knowledge, and enthusiasm among the young generation can be emerged, leading to a larger pool of talented individuals interested in pursuing careers and entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy. This surge in interest can stimulate innovation, promote sustainable practices, and contribute to the growth and development of the bioeconomy sector.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Develop educational programs, campaigns, and outreach initiatives targeting schools, universities, and community organizations to raise awareness and foster interest in bioeconomy-related topics.

The impact of bioeconomy contents in social networks

Quantitative Analysis: This indicator can be analysed by measuring the number of bioeconomy-related social media posts and engagements, tracking the growth rate of such content, evaluating the reach and influence of bioeconomy-related accounts or channels, conducting sentiment analysis to gauge public perception, identifying key influencers and their engagement metrics, and comparing bioeconomy engagement with other relevant topics. As of today, there is no official report which includes a sample big enough to provide a current percentage on the "hype"/"trend" of the topic.

Qualitative Analysis: Implementing targeted social media campaigns, content creation strategies, and influencer partnerships can significantly amplify the impact of bioeconomy-related content on social networks. The expected outcomes include higher visibility, engagement, and dissemination of bioeconomy content to a wider audience. This increased exposure leads to greater public awareness, knowledge, and support for bioeconomy initiatives and practices. It fosters informed discussions, encourages individuals to adopt sustainable behaviours, and influences decision-making processes. By leveraging the power of social networks, the bioeconomy can effectively communicate its value proposition, engage with stakeholders, and mobilize public support for its growth and development.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Implement targeted social media campaigns, content creation strategies, and influencer partnerships to amplify the reach and impact of bioeconomy-related content on social networks.

Mobility support and participation in international projects

Quantitative Analysis: The granting of mobility support for participation in international projects demonstrates a great interest in the subject. Unfortunately, its tracking hasn't been monitored yet

due to the fact that many privacies obstacles surface when searching for the relevant financial information.

Qualitative Analysis: Establishing funding programs and partnerships to support mobility and participation in international projects within the bioeconomy is expected to yield positive outcomes. By providing researchers, professionals, and students with opportunities to engage in international collaborations, exchange programs, and joint initiatives, these efforts foster knowledge exchange, cross-cultural learning, and innovation. The integration of diverse perspectives accelerated progress in bioeconomy research and implementation, and the creation of global networks are only some of the possible outcomes. Through these initiatives, best practices can be shared, research outcomes can be scaled up, and the bioeconomy can benefit from international cooperation, ultimately contributing to its sustainable growth and global impact.

Outcomes and Improvement:

- Establish funding programs and partnerships that support researchers, professionals, and students to participate in international projects, exchange programs, and collaborative initiatives.

2.4.8 *PMT Tool Guidelines*

The Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool (PMT) is a tool designed to help policymakers. It offers guidance on planning and implementing bioeconomy policies, with a special focus on ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) and Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). To effectively use this tool, the steps describe in Figure 10 have to be followed.

Identify the Issue:

Policymakers, including regional authorities, should pinpoint specific concerns related to challenges during the formulation of bioeconomy policies.

Navigate to PMT & Discover Indicator Categories:

Policymakers have the option to delve into five distinct indicator categories, encompassing Ethics, Public Engagement, Socioeconomic, Governance, and Environmental challenges.

Choose & Incorporate Indicators into Your Policy Framework:

It's essential to select and insert suitable indicators to consistently track advancements and evaluate the results of the established policy or strategy.

Learn from PMT's Advice:

For each chosen indicator, the PMT provides detailed textual information informing on the current trends and state-of-play of the chosen indicator in the bioeconomy field.

Integrate PMT's Recommendations into Your Strategy:

Delve into the outcomes and practical advice for the integration of the chosen indicators into your policy framework.

Assess the Outcome:

Employ specific metrics to measure and monitor your indicator, ensuring a thorough evaluation of your policy or strategy's impact.

Figure 10 Policy Monitoring Tool Guide for Policymakers

2.5 Environmental Protection Planning

2.5.1 Introduction

The Environmental Protection Plan (EPP) tool has been developed to support the pollution prevention and control as well as habitat disruption that may occur to the environment. It focuses on assessing the environmental conditions of the regions, recording, and rating the existing barriers and

overall, on improving their performance. To this end, Q-PLAN has developed a set of 32 indicators across the most critical and fundamental environmental management sectors such as the following:

- **Solid waste** concerns dealing with the collection, treatment, and disposal of solid materials that are discarded because they have served their purpose or are no longer useful. The sector seeks to integrate circular practices on the above processes such as recycle, reduce and reuse as well as sustainable solutions for biodegradable solids like composting, waste to energy facilities, etc.
- **Liquid waste** refers to methods for preventing the discharge of pollutants into waterways by collecting and disposing of hazardous liquid items. It mainly concerns the proper operation of the relevant facilities to avoid degradation of the water ecosystem and the blue bioeconomy.
- **Air emissions** refer to atmospheric pollution, which is the contamination of the environment by any chemical, physical, or biological agent that modifies the natural characteristics of the atmosphere. It is also responsible for climate change and contains measures on how to prevent and mitigate it.
- **Water sources** refers to dealing with planning, developing, and properly managing water resources, in terms of both water quantity and quality. Circular bioeconomy principles can be used for optimal management across all water uses.
- **Energy sources** refers to proactive and systematic monitoring, control, and optimization of energy sources to conserve and decrease energy costs. Efficient use of local resources and energy upgrades in the context of bioeconomy are essential for their sustainable management.
- **Green entrepreneurship** concerns creating and implementing solutions to sustainability issues by promoting social change without harming the environment. It involves addressing environmental and social problems and needs with innovative entrepreneurial ideas which are making businesses more sustainable, with a particular focus on the development of circular bioeconomy at regional level.
- **Natural ecosystems** examine the sound existence of living and non-living entities in nature. The sector is focused on the protection of biological resources at urban, peri-urban, rural and forest areas which are crucial for the development of the regional bioeconomy.
- **Sustainable processing** seeks to reduce negative impacts on the environment, and on the health and comfort of living entities. The basic objective is to reduce the consumption of non-renewable resources, to minimise waste and to develop greener value chains and final products with the integration of regional bioeconomy in all the processes.

The EPP current tool is the initial version that will be used within the ROBIN project. It defines the structure and the framework of the tool, as well as the methodology and the guidelines on how the regions can use it. The current version was developed by Q-PLAN was reviewed by MTU and will be operational through Alpha and Beta testing of the ROBIN toolbox in WP3. Afterwards it will be improved after the project's testing activities (validation workshops) from consortium and Advisory Board members.

2.5.2 Literature Review

The development of the indicators has been based on the fundamental aspects of environmental engineering across the most crucial environmental management sectors that have been adjusted for the development of the regional bioeconomy. The overall concept and methodology have been inspired from the existing knowhow and expertise of Q-PLAN as well as the following reports:

- Environmental Protection Plan guidelines and interpretation notes, from the Office of the Regulators of Oil and Gas Operators (OROGO)(2020).
- Environmental Protection Plan, from Ludlow Construction Company, Inc for the US Army Corps of Engineers (Schütz, 2019).

- Environmental Protection Plan Sheboygan River and Harbor Superfund Site Sheboygan County, from US EPA (OROGO, 2019)
- Environmental Protection Plan (EPP), Forteau Quarry, Wharf and Laydown Area from the government of Canada (Ludlow Construction Company, 2019).

The reports were used wisely and under careful consideration to provide insights which were combined with existing knowledge to develop the current version of the tool which is adjusted to the requirements and needs of the ROBIN project.

2.5.3 *Benchmarking*

The main benchmarking on this tool can be found in the following points:

- Develop comprehensive environmental indicators across crucial and essential environmental management sectors that are responsible for sustainable development and are aligned with circular bioeconomy at regional level.
- Develop an environmental assessment with the upcoming barriers indicated across various segments, which should guide the sound implementation of each environmental management sector.
- Deliver actions that will improve the environmental performance of each ROBIN region at the prioritised sectors.
- Structure a training programme which will increase the environmental performance of the ROBIN regions by enhancing the sustainability behaviour of various stakeholders.

2.5.4 *EPP Tool Guidelines*

The EPP tool facilitates the identification of potentially non-eco-friendly practices currently followed by regional authorities. The transition to a bioeconomy requires regional authorities to take action in many ways and improve their environmental management procedures. The current tool can be used by policymakers, their advisors, public servants of all levels, and other practitioners to quickly assess their region's environmental performance and discuss potential actions to adopt more eco-friendly practices.

How it works: The first column of the table lists eight critical environmental management sectors (solid waste, liquid waste, etc.), and the second column shows the most relevant indicators to assess performance in each sector. Users of the tool are invited to read the description of each indicator and select the applicable ones, meaning those that are of interest to the regional authority. Then, after consulting the relevant departments of the regional authority or other local experts if necessary, users report the severity of barriers (technical, financial, etc.) to adopt an eco-friendlier practice in each indicator. Based on the barriers reported, the tool calculates the region's (or municipality's) performance in each indicator and sector. Knowing the performance in each sector, users can easily tell which sectors must be prioritised to find solutions that prevent and control pollution and habitat disruption. Finally, users are invited to discuss actions that potentially address the identified challenges. The BE-Rural resources and the ROBIN project deliverables may help in this respect. Also, users are welcome to contact the ROBIN website for any questions or clarifications.

Descriptions are also in place and will be very useful for the regional authorities to understand the context of the indicator and to assess its status. The 32 indicators (4 for each environmental management sector) can be seen below.

I. **Solid Waste**

- Waste sorting – it examines if the region implements different bins into the collection of various waste (organic, plastic, glass, paper).

- Waste management – checks if the region applies a proper waste management into the process of collection-transportation-disposal-treatment and how the region would rate it.
- Biodegradable facilities – identifies if these facilities exist in the region and if so how advanced are these treatment methods. Some examples are composting, fertilizer, biogas, and other waste to energy initiatives.
- Hazardous waste – checks if there is a special treatment for such waste (pharmaceuticals, drugs, industrial waste, chemicals treatment, etc.) It is important that the regions treat the hazardous waste appropriately because they have a high rate of contamination which can degrade the natural ecosystems and destroy the local biological resources that are required for the development of the regional bioeconomy.

II. Liquid Waste

- Wastewater treatment plant – seeks to find if there is such a facility and where the region disposes of such waste. Discarding it without any treatment is catastrophic for the aquatic ecosystem.
- Outlet monitoring – if it is monitored and is aligned with the standards to prevent the above contamination.
- Recirculation facility – such solutions can apply circularity measures to reduce energy and make the overall process more efficient.
- Outlet disposal ecosystem – checks if the region is aware of the degradation risk of blue bioeconomy resources and if protection measures are in place. Blue bioeconomy sources such as algae, sponges, jellyfish, or other microorganisms are useful for the creation of bio-based products and bioenergy.

III. Energy Resources

- Biomass potential & local exploitation – examines if the region is aware of the potential of its various biomass streams and if local biomass exploitation is taking place efficiently.
- Biorefineries – if there are any biorefineries in the region and if they could be more oriented towards the above biomass potential.
- Bioenergy innovations – checks if those are applicable in the region with the form of liquid, solid and/or gaseous biofuels, bioheat, bioelectricity, etc.
- Energy saving measures – identifies if the region applies those measures or implements such policies. Biomass should be considered in these measures. i.e., biomass boilers in buildings, biomethane to natural gas grid, bioenergy in co-generation processes, etc.

IV. Natural Ecosystems

- Biodiversity preservation – checks if the region protects and properly maintains local biodiversity like lakes, rivers, parks, etc.
- Forest protection – identifies if the region properly cleans, protects, and maintains the local forests and if they exploit the forest residues and checks whether they have fire protection measures and zones.
- Animal and wildlife protection – investigates if there are organisations and/or policies that protect animals in the various areas.
- Sound pollution – if the region considers sound pollution at urban and industrial environments and if they apply any mitigation measures on such environments.

V. Green Entrepreneurship

- Environmental Governance – investigates if the regional authority has a Bioeconomy strategy and/or a Circular Economy action plan, if it follows the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, etc. It also assesses if these measures are applicable at the urban level as well, through the governance of municipalities.
- Sustainable Finance – investigates if the regional authority respects the ESG metrics (Environmental, Social and Governance). It also assesses if the entities are using sustainability reports and if some funding is provided based on these. Here the regions should consider the corporate and industrial implementation.
- Eco-Management Systems – checks if the regional authorities, organisations, industries, companies, etc. are certified with the respective management systems i.e., ISO 14001, 50001, 26001, etc.
- Regional policy – examines how the regional governance bodies apply environmentally friendly policies, and if the same takes place also at the urban and municipal level.

VI. Sustainable Processing

- Sustainable Product design – checks if the products are certified with eco-labels and if the industries apply environmental measures for their production.
- Bioproducts & biomaterials – investigates if the region produces bio-products and biomaterials, and if the quantity aligns with the biomass potential.
- Sustainable Logistics – examines the sustainability of the following processes: Biomass collection - distribution - storage - biorefinery feed - processes - production - packaging - distribution - consumption - disposal. If sufficient data cannot be provided, estimations can be used.
- Bio-based value chains – investigates if biomass innovation is included in the above processes.

VII. Water Resources

- Drinking facilities – Assesses if water quality control (physical, chemical, biological properties) is in place in the region.
- Water management – Checks if there are any recirculation facilities for reducing water consumption.
- Urban precipitation run off – Investigates if there are any collection systems to sustainably manage rain or snow.
- Blue economy – Assess if the region is investigating its natural aquatic resources for bioeconomy development e.g., for biofuels, food additives or pharmaceuticals.

VIII. Air Emissions

- GHGs monitoring – investigates if GHG emissions are monitored through the main activities of the region.
- Air exposure limits – checks if air exposure limits are measured at the city level.
- Atmospheric wellbeing – assesses if citizens have a well-being based on the exposure levels and international standards.
- Sector Decarbonization – investigates if the region has a specific plan for decarbonization of its different sectors.

The draft figure of the Excel version of the EPP Tool can be seen in Figure 11 below:

Barriers	
Crucial	↑
Significant	↔
Minor	↓
None	

Environmental Performance	
Excellent	8-10
Sufficient	6-8
Weak	4-6
Poor	2-4
Unacceptable	0-2

ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION PLAN													
Environmental Management Sectors	Environmental Indicators	Description	Applicability	Barriers					Environmental Performance	Sectoral Assessment	Comments	Priority for the region	Suggested Actions & training needs
				Technical	Financial	Skills & Knowledge	Policy & Regulations	Local awareness					
Solid Waste	Waste sorting	Does your region implement different bins into the collection of urban waste (organic, plastic, glass, paper)?							0	0.00			
	Waste management	Does your region have a proper process for the waste management collection, transportation, disposal of waste? How waste is treated in your region? How advanced are these treatment methods? (i.e. Composting, Incineration, Biogas, etc.)						0					
	Biodegradable facilities	Do you apply a special treatment for the bio-waste (spatiotemporally, through industrial waste, chemical, treatment, etc.)?						0					
	Hazardous waste	Do you have a Waste Water Treatment Plant? Where is the liquid waste disposed?						0					
Liquid Waste	Waste water treatment plant	Do you monitor the outlet to be aligned with the standard?						0	0.00				
	Outlet monitoring	Do you monitor the outlet to be aligned with the standard?						0					
	Recirculation facility	Do you apply any recirculation facility to reduce the concentration efficiency?						0					
Air Emissions	GHGs monitoring	Consider how the risk to decarbonize the blue bioeconomy ecosystem. Do you have any projection strategy on GHG, etc.?						0	0.00				
	Air exposure limits	Do you monitor the GHG emissions through the main activities of your region? (i.e. industrial, transportation, building, etc.)						0					
	Atmospheric well being	Do you measure especially at city level the concentration - exposure level?						0					
	Sectoral decarbonisation	Does your region have a specific plan for the decarbonisation of the sector? (i.e. industrial, buildings, transport, etc.)						0					
Water resources	Drinking water facilities	Do you investigate and/or exploit the natural aquatic resources for bioeconomy value addition, food systems, pharmaceuticals, etc.?						0	0.00				
	Water management	Do you collect and/or manage sustainably the wastewater and/or? Do you apply any recirculation facilities, reduction of water consumption, reuse (WATER4ALL)?						0					
	Urban precipitation runoff	Do you investigate and/or exploit the natural aquatic resources for bioeconomy value addition, food systems, pharmaceuticals, etc.?						0					
Energy resources	Biomass potential & local exploitation	Are you aware of the biomass potential in your area? Does the local biomass exploitation allow it? Do you have any beneficiaries? For what purposes? Could you have more with the local biomass available?						0	0.00				
	Biorefineries	Which of those do you apply in your area? (Ethanol, Biogas, Bioplastics, etc.)						0					
	Energy saving measures	Does your region apply these measures or implements such policies? Biomass should be considered as these measures (i.e. biomass).						0					
Natural Ecosystems	Biodiversity preservation	Do you protect and maintain the local biodiversity (rivers, lakes, parks, etc.)?						0	0.00				
	Forests protection	Do you have properly protect and maintain the forests in your area? Do you exploit the forest products? Have you any initiatives?						0					
	Animals and wildlife protection	Do you have regulations and/or policies that protect the animals in your area? (i.e. WILDLIFE4ALL)?						0					
	Sound pollution	Do you measure the sound pollution in urban and industrial environments and do you apply reduction measures?						0					
Green Entrepreneurship	Environmental Governance	Does your regional authority have a Bioeconomy Strategy, Circular Economy action plan, Sustainable development plan, etc. that does regional authority respects the SDG metrics? Are the entities using sustainability metrics to measure their performance in your region? (local authority and organizations).						0	0.00				
	Sustainable Finance	Do you have any beneficiaries? For what purposes? Could you have more with the local biomass available?						0					
	Eco Management Systems	Do you have any beneficiaries? For what purposes? Could you have more with the local biomass available?						0					
	Regional policy	Do you have any beneficiaries? For what purposes? Could you have more with the local biomass available?						0					
Sustainable Processing	Sustainable Product design	Do the products certified with eco labels? Do the industries apply environmental measures (i.e. WASTE4ALL)?						0	0.00				
	Bioproducts & biomaterials	What kind of bioproducts and biomaterials produce your region? How much quantity is related with the biomass available? How much is related with the biomass available?						0					
	Sustainable Logistics	Biomass collection - distribution - storage - biorefinery - biogas - bioplastics - biodegradation - bio.						0					
	Bio based value chains	Do you include in the processes? Biomass collection - distribution - storage - biorefinery - biogas - bioplastics - biodegradation - bio.						0					

Figure 11 ROBIN Environmental Protection Planning Tool

The tool has been created based on the fundamental aspects of environmental engineering and has been adjusted to operate within the principles of the regional bioeconomy. Figure 12 explains the rationale followed to develop this tool. The EPP tool has been divided into two main categories: the environmental management sectors upon which the environmental assessment will take place, and the environmental training schedule. The former refers to the development of the 32 environmental indicators that have been developed across 8 core environmental management sectors, and the assessment methodology that explained above.

The environmental training schedule is being developed based on the regional needs of each ROBIN area and includes the training programs from the BE-Rural project (BE-Rural, 2019). The overall training plan needs to give special emphasis to the needs of each area, covering topics like the environmental sustainability, circular bioeconomy, waste management and circularity, bioeconomy strategy, etc. The whole environmental protection plan has been adjusted to the principles of circular economy and bioeconomy and to be operational at the regional level covering urban, peri-urban, rural, agricultural, forestry lands and industrial areas.

Figure 12 Tool development rationale

After filling in the fields of the EPP tool, the main outcome is a list of suggested actions for every ROBIN region, with special focus on the prioritised environmental management sectors and aiming to significantly contribute to the overall improvement of their environmental performance. The updated version after the 1st validation workshop and the Alpha testing round, and even more the final version after the 2nd validation workshop and the Beta testing, will represent a strong tool for various regions across Europe. In practice, it will help them to assess, monitor and improve their environmental performance by making sound environmental protection plans. This tool will also provide valuable insights for the development of the other ROBIN tools like the Policy Monitoring System and the final Governance Model both of which will include an environmental domain and will receive feedback and findings from the Environmental Protection Plan.

2.5.5 Further tool updates

The EPP tool will be tested as part of the ROBIN Toolbox within the 2 rounds of the project (Alpha and Beta testing). After each round a validation workshop will take place where consortium partners along with the Advisory Board members will discuss and analyse the findings of each testing round, to spot malfunctions, potentials for improvement, unnecessary actions, etc. The goal is to make a final version of the ROBIN Toolbox (which contains 3 tools, one of which is the EPP tool) that will be used from regions across Europe to establish, monitor and enhance regional bioeconomy's.

So, the expected subsequent versions are the following:

- Updated version of the ROBIN Toolbox and consequently of the EPP tool after the 1st validation workshop by M24.
- Final version of the ROBIN Toolbox and consequently of the EPP tool after the 2nd validation workshop by M32.

2.6 Support Action Portfolio

The Support Action Portfolio (SAP) has been integrated into the toolbox as a valuable resource, offering examples for inspiration to assist other regions in their capacity-building endeavors. This insight originates from the efforts undertaken in Task 2.2, during which support action plans were formulated by the ROBIN regions. A comprehensive account of this development is available in the project's deliverable D2.2 "ROBIN Regions Action Plans."

The development of the portfolio was an iterative and collaborative work of sequential phases in the regional co-creation process involving MARC members and other stakeholders within WP2. The final SAP tool includes a total of 49 inspirational actions. These actions were categorized into 16 regional analysis measures, 20 social measures and 13 technical measures.

For the analogue version of the SAP tool, the information was collected and presented as an Excel Table (Figure 13), which includes the following information:

- Type of measure (Regional Analysis, Social or Technical)
- Internal code system
- Title of the support action
- Description of the support action, outlining its purpose, methodology, and anticipated outcomes.
- ROBIN region/s where the support action is either partially or fully included in their regional action plan.

TYPE	CODE	TITLE	DESCRIPTION	ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	REGION
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM1	Identification of relevant actors/project promoters/change agents at regional level	Identification of relevant actors or project promoters or change agents is a crucial step in the development of a regional bioeconomy strategy analysis. This action aims to gather information on the various educational programs, research centers, and organizations in the region.	AND, ZIL	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM2	Identification of educational offer in bioeconomy at regional level	This action aims to gather information on the various educational programs, research centers, and organizations in the region.	AND, BW, SRA	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM3	Analysis of biomass resources and potential	This action involves gathering and examining data on various sources of biomass resources and their potential for use in the bioeconomy.	RCM, SRA, ZIL, AND	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM4	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at governance level	The analysis of barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at the governance level involves identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the regional level.	RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM5	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at technical level	The analysis of barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at a technical level involves identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the technical level.	AND, RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM6	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at legal and normative level	The task involves conducting an analysis of the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the legal and normative level.	AND, RCM, SRA	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM7	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at end-user level	The analysis of barriers to the deployment of the bioeconomy at the end-user level involves identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the end-user level.	RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM8	Analysis of relevant regional strategies and legislation	A comprehensive analysis of relevant regional strategies and legislation is conducted to identify and map the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the regional level.	AND, RCM, SRA	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM9	Regional bioeconomy strategy analysis	The regional bioeconomy strategy analysis is a comprehensive examination of the current governance framework in place and the identification of potential avenues for securing funding within a specific region.	AND, RCM, BW	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM10	Implementation of regional bioeconomy strategy analysis	The implementation of a regional bioeconomy strategy analysis involves a comprehensive examination of the current governance framework in place and the identification of potential avenues for securing funding within a specific region.	AND, RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM11	Analysis of regional funding mechanisms and instruments (public level)	This analysis aims to provide a detailed understanding of the various ways in which funding is provided at the regional level.	AND, ZIL, RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM12	Analysis of regional financing opportunities (private initiatives)	The objective is to identify potential avenues for securing funding within a specific region.	AND, RCM, SRA	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM13	Identification of bioeconomy research infrastructures at regional level	The objective of this action is to identify and map the bioeconomy research infrastructures at the regional level.	AND, RCM	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM14	Analysis of the use of the bioeconomy research infrastructures at regional level	The analysis of the use of bioeconomy research infrastructures at the regional level involves identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the regional level.		
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM15	Analysis of the existing bioeconomy governance structure in the region	The analysis will begin by examining the current governance framework in place and the identification of potential avenues for securing funding within a specific region.	AND, BW, RCM, SRA	
REGIONAL ANALYSIS MEASURES	RAM16	Identification of bioeconomy good practices at regional level	The objective of this action is to identify and document bioeconomy good practices at the regional level.	AND, ZIL, BW	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM1	Development of a bioeconomy awareness raising strategy	This activity involves creating a comprehensive plan to educate and engage stakeholders in the bioeconomy strategy of the region.	AND, ZIL, SRA, BW	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM2	Stakeholder engagement: local authorities	The process of engaging local authorities begins with identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the local level.	SRA, RCM	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM3	Stakeholder engagement: private sector	Some effective ways to engage the private sector in the bioeconomy strategy of the region are identified and mapped.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM4	Stakeholder engagement: academia	Stakeholder engagement with academia refers to the process of involving academic institutions in the bioeconomy strategy of the region.	RCM	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM5	Stakeholder engagement: civil society	Stakeholder engagement is a crucial aspect of any decision-making process, and it involves identifying and mapping the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the civil society level.	AND, BW	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM6	Networking activities among relevant regional stakeholders	These activities aim to bring together individuals, organizations, and institutions in the region to share knowledge and resources.	AND, BW, ZIL, RCM	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM7	Creation of a stable advisory board group with representatives of the Quadruple Helix	The primary objective of this advisory board group is to provide guidance and support to the regional bioeconomy strategy analysis.	AND, SRA	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM8	Development of social innovation methodologies and tools	Social innovation refers to the process of developing and implementing new ideas, products, or services that address societal challenges.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM9	Development of communication material for local authorities and policy makers	The action will involve a comprehensive understanding of the target audience and the development of communication material that is tailored to their needs.	IBW, RCM	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM10	Development of communication material for private sector	The task at hand involves the development of communication material specific to the private sector.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM11	Development of communication material for students (high school, VET, university)	The task at hand involves the development of communication material specific to students.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM12	Development of communication material for end-users	The task at hand involves the development of communication material specific to end-users.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM13	Development of communication material for general civil society	The task involves the comprehensive development of communication material for the general civil society.	AND, BW	
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM14	Competing brain drain through new bioeconomy business models in rural areas	According to the online Eurostat publications "Rural Europe" and "Urban Europe", the brain drain in rural areas is a significant challenge.		
SOCIAL MEASURES	SM15	Business support and social entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy remit	Support instruments such as the Green National Champions Program in Hungary and the Green National Champions Program in Hungary are identified and mapped.	RCM	

Figure 13 Support Action Portfolio- Analogue Excel table

3. ROBIN Digital Toolbox

3.1 Wireframe and structure definition

In the preliminary stages of the toolbox's website development, the focus was on creating a wireframe and structure to be able to integrate various technologies effectively while providing a user-friendly experience (See Annex 4.1). For this, existing online tools dedicated to bioeconomy were used as inspiration. The project partners involved in WP2 collaborated in defining and finalizing the wireframe's structure. This approach ensured each section's optimal design to meet the specific requirements of every component (i.e. Knowledge Platform, Tools and Support Actions Portfolio)

The wireframe was designed to support dynamic content updates and user interaction therefore we opted for [WordPress](#). This decision facilitated the website development and content management since the toolbox will be further updated during the course of the project and especially after the alpha and beta testing iterations.

The integration of social media platforms like [Facebook](#), [X](#), and [LinkedIn](#) was of paramount importance in order to promote the visibility of the toolbox along with the project's original social media platforms and website, adding the appropriate redirection links.

By choosing widgets and plugins with a particular emphasis on those which increase Search Engine Optimization (SEO) ([Yoast Plugins](#)) and site search capabilities ([Sitelinks Search Box](#)), we intend to maximize the website's visibility and reach. We also utilized Viewport Meta for a seamless adaptation of the toolbox's website to various device screens.

3.2 Technical functionalities

Outlined below is a description of all the essential technical features, functionalities, and plugins that were used to complete the website's efficiency and user experience. These elements collectively ensure that our site is not only functionally robust but also easily navigable.

- **SEO Optimization:** We utilize Yoast Plugins to enhance our site's SEO. This helps in refining page content, image titles, meta descriptions, and boosts our overall search engine presence.
- **Search Feature:** Our site features Google's Sitelinks Search Box for enhanced search functionality, allowing users to find content efficiently.
- **Content Management System:** Our website is powered by the latest version of WordPress (6.2), providing us with extensive content management capabilities.
- **Mobile Responsiveness:** The website features mobile optimization tools like Viewport Meta and compatibility for iPhone and other mobile devices, ensuring a seamless mobile experience.
- **JavaScript and CSS Integration:** We employ [jQuery](#) for interactive user elements and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) for aesthetic presentation.
- **Social Media Integration:** Includes direct mentions and links to social platforms, enhancing the site's engagement.
- **Privacy and Compliance:** There is adherence to privacy standards with the '*Do Not Sell My Personal Information*' policy by including the relevant shortcode, respecting user data privacy.
- **Accessibility and Web Standards:** Compliance with [WAI-ARIA](#) for accessibility and uses [HTML5](#) standards, ensuring adherence to modern web practices.
- **Innovative Web Technologies:** Features like [Open Graph Protocol](#), [Twitter Cards](#), and [JSON-LD](#), were employed to enhance user interaction.

Additionally, the website utilizes several specific plugins for greater functionality:

- [Avada Theme](#) for the overall website design.
- [PDF Flipbook, 3D Flipbook – DearFlip](#) for interactive PDF viewing.
- [ACF: Better Search and Advanced Custom Fields PRO](#) for enhanced search functionality and custom field management.
- [Category Ajax Filter Pro](#) for dynamic content filtering.
- [CookieYes | GDPR Cookie Consent](#) for compliance with GDPR requirements.
- [Image Hotspot by DevVN](#) for interactive image features.
- [Interactive Geo Maps](#) for visual representation of geographic data.
- [Site Kit by Google](#) for integrated Google services and analytics.

3.3 Description of the ROBIN digital toolbox sections

The digital toolbox is organized into distinct sections, including the Main page, User Guidelines, Knowledge Platform, Tools, and Support Actions. Each section comprises subpages providing detailed information on specific aspects, ensuring a comprehensive overview of the toolbox's features.

3.3.1 Main page

The main site of the ROBIN toolbox is structured to provide a comprehensive understanding of the toolbox's resources. It features a header and main menu for easy navigation and includes a detailed description of the ROBIN toolbox, explaining the purpose and functionality of each component within the "Description of toolbox" section.

Figure 14 Screenshot of the ROBIN Toolbox main page

Additionally, the site showcases a roadmap diagram (Figure 15) which visually represents the interconnection of the toolbox's various elements, offering users a clear pathway through the

toolbox's features. It includes three main components, namely "Knowledge Platform," "Tools," and "Support Actions Portfolio," each branching into specific components like "Regional Governance Models," "Circular Bioeconomy Model Canvas," and "Support Actions List," indicating its interconnectedness. When positioning the mouse on each section a short description of the tool is shown and there is also a direct link to the tool site.

Figure 15 Screenshot of the toolbox roadmap

The ROBIN Toolbox's main page is available under: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/>

In formulating the toolbox roadmap, several considerations were taken into account to address potential needs at different stages of planning and implementing bioeconomy governance models in the regions. For instance, the Knowledge Platform provides valuable insights and inspiration through examples of regional governance models and good practices, facilitating initial planning and development. The Circular Bioeconomy Model Canvas proves beneficial for both the development and updating of bioeconomy governance models. Evaluating the performance of governance models in terms of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) aspects is facilitated by the Policy Monitoring Tool. For a targeted analysis of environmental practices, the Environmental Protection Tool stands as a valuable support. Furthermore, to facilitate the formulation of concrete action plans in areas such as raising stakeholder awareness and engagement, the Support Action Portfolio proves to be an ideal source of inspiration.

To enhance user usability and understanding, a dedicated section with guidelines was also defined, which is presented in the subsequent section.

3.3.2 User guidelines

The user guidelines for the ROBIN toolbox serve as a compass, aiming to empower users by providing clear insights into the functionalities of each tool based on their specific needs. Through a series of questions and suggestions, users are guided to unlock the potential of the toolbox, making it a tailored resource. Additionally, a glossary has been included to explain specific terminology, ensuring that users can navigate the toolbox with a clear understanding. A screenshot of the guidelines page is presented in Figure 16.

User Guidelines

Are you just starting to plan how your bioeconomy governance model will work? [↻](#)

Visit the ROBIN Knowledge Platform ([Governance Models](#), [Good Practices](#)) to provide valuable insights and best practices to start

Are you currently putting your bioeconomy governance model into action? [↻](#)

Are you currently keeping track of how well your bioeconomy governance model is working? [↻](#)

Are you looking for inspiration and best practices in bioeconomy governance? [↻](#)

Do you need practical tools and templates to streamline the development of your governance model? [↻](#)

Are you interested in accessing case studies and reports on successful regional bioeconomy governance models? [↻](#)

Do you require support in policy monitoring? [↻](#)

Do you require support in environmental protection planning? [↻](#)

Are you seeking customized resources that are applicable to your specific territorial context? [↻](#)

Glossary

- Bioeconomy**
Bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources from land and sea, like crops, forests, fish, animals, and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy.
(Source: Bioeconomy (europa.eu))
- Governance Model**
- Good practice**
- Good governance practices**
- Policy monitoring**
- Environmental protection plan**
- Support action**
- Action plan**
- Regional bioeconomy strategy**
- Regional vision/Value proposition**
- Support Actions Portfolio**
- Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas**

Figure 16 Screenshot of the user guidelines site

The user guidelines are available under: [User Guideline - Robin Toolbox \(auth.gr\)](#)

3.3.3 Knowledge Platform

Governance Models

The Governance Models tool (Figure 17 and Figure 18) is a comprehensive resource offering an array of circular bioeconomy governance models for regional deployment throughout the EU. It incorporates various typological aspects including governance mechanisms, constraints, territorial factors, and sustainability goals. In the digital version users can explore 20 available models with a search function and filters, including country, territorial aspects, transformation paths, and governance strategies. Additionally, it visually presents the regions on maps to showcase where each model is being applied.

Governance Models

Resource that provides a collection of diverse circular bioeconomy governance models designed for regional implementation across the EU. It considers varying typology aspects such as governance mechanism and constrains, territorial aspects, sustainability objectives among others.

Country [v](#)

Territorial Aspect [v](#)

Transformation Path [v](#)

Enabling Governance Mechanism [v](#)

Constraining Governance [v](#)

Territorial Measure [v](#)

Strategy [v](#)

Focus [v](#)

Alliance Plant³

Germany / Mecklenburg - Pomerania. The Alliance Plant³ Aims At Making A Substantial Contribution To An Innovation-Based Structural Change In The North-Eastern Mecklenburg - Pomerania Region. It Is An Open...

[Read More](#)

Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy

Spain / Andalusia. Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) Contributes To The Sustainable Growth And Competitiveness Of The Region. The Focus Of The ACBS Is The Development Of Activities Among Three...

[Read More](#)

Filter Description:

- Country:** Where the governance model is implemented/studied.
- Territorial Aspect:** Specific geographical or spatial characteristics of a region where the governance model is applied.
- Transformation Path:** The strategic direction or approach taken in the bioeconomy sector.
- Enabling Governance Mechanism:** Proactive strategies/tools that bolster the development and implementation of the bioeconomy.
- Constraining Governance:** Mechanisms that set limits, standards, or address potential challenges in the bioeconomy.
- Territorial Measure:** Actions/policies tailored to the unique needs and characteristics of a particular territory.
- Strategy:** High-level plan/approach designed to achieve specific goals.
- Focus:** Highlights the primary area or sector of interest within the bioeconomy

Figure 17 Screenshot of Governance Models site

Alliance Plant³

The Alliance Plant³ aims at making a substantial contribution to an innovation-based structural change in the north-eastern Mecklenburg - Pomerania region. It is an open innovation network and it acts as think tank for new ideas and academic support of next value chains based on bioeconomy. The initiative should be seen as model for sustainable transformation of the rural areas, since this region is mainly agricultural and coastal.

-	Description
This is an alliance of to support the research and development on bioeconomy, as well as the "Structure Turnaround" in this former region of the German Democratic Republic. It was initiated by a public-private partnership composed of a university, the regional investment agency and a company. It is funded by the German national programme WIRI. It has regional focus in Pomerania. It is supported by an Advisory Council, so the work of the Alliance is aligned with the regional strategy and funding priorities of the programme WIRI. It has a Steering Group that monitors the calls and evaluate the proposals.	
+	Environmental Objectives
+	Economic Objectives
+	Societal Objectives
+	Key Actors
+	Further Information

Figure 18 Example of governance model of the list

The governance models' site is available under:

<https://obintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/governance-models/>

Good Practices

The Good Practices Tool (Figure 19 and Figure 20) is a repository of successful strategies employed by regional governments to foster social innovation and circular bioeconomy business models. It provides regions with information that can help as inspiration to shape their bioeconomy strategies effectively, such as developing policy monitoring systems and environmental protection plans. The digital tool features 10 documented practices, along with a filter function that allows users to sort these practices by country and type. A search function enhances the user experience by enabling easy access to specific practices. Additionally, the tool includes maps that visually display the regions where these good practices have been implemented.

Good Practices

Resource with successful good practices of regional government to encourage social innovation and business models to promote circular bioeconomy.

Search

Countries ▼

Type Of Practice ▼

Baden-Württemberg Bioeconomy Congress

Germany / Baden-Württemberg. In The Congress Important Topics Regarding Bioeconomy Are Addressed By Information Sessions, Discussion Panels, Workshops, Excursions, And Seminars Including Real-Life Practices.

[Read More](#)

BIOVALE Innovation Camp

UK / Yorkshire And Humberland. The Innovation Biocamp Funded Through The Biobase4SME Programme Was A Week-Long Incubator Programme Operating Between 2017 And 2019 Aimed At Providing High-Potential Biobased Companies With...

[Read More](#)

Filter Description:

- **Countries:** Nation/states where good governance practices are implemented and/or studied.
- **Type of Practice:** Specific approach/method used in overseeing the bioeconomy within a particular region and/or context.

Figure 19 Screenshot of Good Practices site

Edible Landscape Project CLG

The Edible Landscapes Project has devised a novel Education Program for Irish primary schools to encourage more schoolchildren to grow and consume food in an environmentally sustainable, climate smart way. This solution focused, Food Forest: Climate Education Program was developed by teachers, for teachers, and in November 2021 was launched in local primary schools in Co. Mayo.

Description
Empowering local communities to engage positively with climate change through education. The Edible Landscape Project want to make ethical decision making regarding food choices and have integrity in everything they do. Understanding that the issue of climate change has become a worrying and growing issue recently. Some children are very concerned or anxious and the program we have compiled is intended to be a positive, solutions-based approach to the issue. Each of the strand units and learning outcomes are clearly stated as they are in the curriculum, to assist lesson planning. Participating primary school teachers receive a pack containing a set of Lesson Plans which are directly curriculum linked. The resources provided are intended to teach students how our food choices can have both a positive and negative impact on climate change. The Edible Landscape Project have devised a novel Education Program for Irish primary schools to encourage more schoolchildren to grow and consume food in an environmentally sustainable, climate smart way. This solution focused, Food Forest: Climate Education Program was developed by teachers, for teachers, and in November 2021 was launched in local primary schools in Co. Mayo.
Environmental Impact
Social Impact
Economic Impact
Further Information

Figure 20 Example of a good practice of the list

The governance models' site is available under: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/good-practices/>

3.3.4 Tools

Circular Bioeconomy Model Canvas (CBMC)

The digital version of the CBGMC tool (Figure 21) has been developed to enhance the user experience and provide comprehensive support.

+ User Guidelines

Figure 21 Screenshot of the digital version of the CBMC

The key features and functionalities of the CBGMC Tool include:

- **One-Page Navigation:** The entire tool is accessible on a single page, eliminating the need for users to switch between different pages or sections, providing a more focused and uninterrupted experience.
- **Hover for Information:** As users move their cursor over each segment of the canvas, they are presented with additional information relevant to that segment. This interactive element provides immediate access to information that should be filled in or considered for each part of the canvas. It serves as a clear and on-the-spot reference.
- **Downloadable Canvas in Multiple Formats:** The canvas is available for download in various formats, catering to the different needs of users. These formats include PDF and JPEG, offering flexibility in how the canvas is used and shared. Additionally, the tool provides both a blank canvas and a guided version. The blank canvas allows for complete customization, while the guided version offers a clear and structured guidance on its usage.
- **Support and Guidance for Implementation:** To assist users in effectively implementing the tool, the webpage includes comprehensive support information in the form of a user guide, which can be downloaded directly from the webpage, supporting the user in implementing the tool.

CBGMC Tool available under: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/circular-bioeconomy-governance-model-canvas/>

Policy Monitoring Tool (PMT)

The digital version of the PMT has been developed to provide a straightforward interface, allowing users to navigate its material with ease and efficiency. Key features of the digital tool include an efficient navigation system that is clear and guides users through the process of accessing and analyzing policy indicators, and a responsive design which ensures accessibility and functionality across various devices and screen sizes. The tool presents the data in a clear and concise manner using descriptive text. It provides comprehensive information and explanations about the selected indicators and offers insights and interpretations of the data. A screenshot of the current form of the tool can be viewed in Figure 22 and an example of an indicator's page in Figure 23.

Figure 22 Screenshot of the digital version of the PMT

Employment by age in bioeconomy sectors

This indicator offers insights into the age distribution of the workforce within bioeconomy sectors. It assesses the composition of employees in various age groups, helping to identify trends and potential generational differences in bioeconomy employment. The data can inform strategies accordingly, ameliorating its workforce development and planning.

Qualitative Analysis	<p>The bioeconomy relies on the expertise and experience of older workers who have accumulated valuable knowledge in areas such as agriculture, forestry, and biotechnology. However, attracting and retaining younger workers in the bioeconomy is challenging due to limited awareness and understanding of the career opportunities available in this field.</p> <p>The diverse industries within the bioeconomy, such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and bioproduct manufacturing, may not be widely recognized or considered appealing career paths for younger individuals. This lack of awareness contributes to the difficulty in attracting younger talent to the sector.</p> <p>Furthermore, ageism and discriminatory practices during the hiring process pose additional obstacles for younger individuals seeking employment in the bioeconomy. Older workers may be favored based on assumptions of their experience and reliability, while younger candidates may face biases related to perceived lack of experience or maturity.</p>
Quantitative Analysis	
Outcomes & Improvement	
Evaluation Metric*	

Figure 23 Screenshot of one PMT page as example

PMT Tool available under: [https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/policy-monitoring-system/Environmental Planning Tool \(EPP\)](https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/policy-monitoring-system/Environmental Planning Tool (EPP))

The digital version of the EPP tools has been developed to allow policymakers and related actors to use this tool for their regions. Its key feature and functionality include an Excel-based interface, making it accessible and familiar to many users as well as user guidelines, facilitating the ease of use of the tool. The tool also contains user guidelines to support the users to complete the tool with their region's information. Descriptions are included for each environmental indicator across the key sectors, to allow the user to assess each indicator on a case-by-case basis for their region. Based on the environmental performance applied to each indicator, a sectoral assessment is auto calculated for each sector, and these are comparable by each sector in table format at the bottom of the tool, to highlight the key priority areas.

ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION PLAN												
Environmental Management Sectors	Environmental Indicators	Description	Applicability	Barriers					Environmental Performance	Sectoral Assessment	Comments	
				Technical	Financial	Skills & Knowledge	Policy & Regulations	Local awareness				
	Waste sorting	Does your region implement different bins into the collection of various waste (organic, plastic, glass, paper)?							0	0.00		
	Waste management	Do they use in your region have advanced and those treatment methods? (e.g. collection-transportation-disposal-treatment)						0				
	Biodegradable facilities	Do they use in your region have advanced and those treatment methods? (e.g. hazardous waste (pharmaceuticals, drugs, industrial waste, chemicals) treatment, hazardous waste (pharmaceuticals, drugs, industrial waste, chemicals) treatment,							0			
	Hazardous waste	Do you have a Waste Water Treatment Plant? Where is the liquid waste disposed?							0			
	Waste water treatment plant	Do you monitor the outlet to be aligned with the standards?							0	0.00		
	Outlet monitoring	Do you apply any recirculation facility to reduce the concentration efficiency?							0			
	Recirculation facility	Consider here the risk to restore the local bioeconomy ecosystem. Do you have any appropriate measures to deal with it?							0			
	Outlet disposal ecosystem	the main activities of your region? (e.g. industrial, transportation, building, energy)							0			
	GHGs monitoring	Do you measure especially at city level the concentration - exposure level?							0	0.00		
	Air exposure limits	Do the criteria have well being based on the exposure levels and international							0			
	Atmospheric well being	Do you have any measures to deal with it? (e.g. buildings stock, industries, transport,							0			
	Sectorial decarbonisation	In your region the water quality control being strict? (e.g. monitoring physical, chemical and biological characteristics)							0			
	Drinking water facilities	Do you apply any recirculation facilities, reduction of water consumption, reuse policies, etc?							0	0.00		
	Water management	Do you collect and/or manage sustainably the rain/flow, etc?							0			
	Urban precipitation runoff	natural aquatic resources for bioeconomy system (fisheries, forest activities,							0			
	Blue bioeconomy	Do you intend to the bottom potential in							0			
Energy resources	Biomass potential & local											

User Guidelines

Figure 24 Screenshot of the digital version of the EPP

EPP Tool available under: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/environmental-protection-planning/>

3.3.5 Support Action Portofolio

Support Action Portofolio

The Support Action Portofolio (Figure 25 and Figure 26) serves as a repository of examples for creating action plans that enhance regional capacity. It is designed to aid in areas like boosting stakeholder awareness and involvement. This tool offers a filtering function by the type of measure, allowing users to easily navigate through the different support actions. It includes a comprehensive list of 49 actions derived from the experiences and practices of the ROBIN regions: Andalusia, Central Macedonia, Baden-Wuerttemberg, Southern Region Ireland, and Zilina.

Figure 25 Screenshot of Support Action Portofolio site

Analysis of biomass resources and potential

This action involves gathering and examining data on various sources of biomass, such as agricultural residues, forestry waste, and energy crops, to determine their availability and suitability for different applications. The first step in this process is to collect data on the quantity and quality of biomass resources in a given region. This may involve conducting surveys, consulting existing databases, and collaborating with relevant stakeholders such as farmers, foresters, and energy companies. The collected data is then analyzed to identify the most abundant and accessible biomass resources. Next, the analysis focuses on assessing the potential of these resources for different uses. This includes evaluating their energy content, moisture content, and chemical composition to determine their suitability for conversion into biofuels, biogas, or other forms of renewable energy. The analysis also considers factors such as transportation logistics, infrastructure requirements, and environmental impacts to identify the most viable options for biomass utilization. In addition to energy production, the analysis may also explore other potential applications of biomass resources. For example, certain types of biomass may be suitable for the production of bio-based materials, such as bioplastics or biochar, which can help reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate climate change. The output of this analysis is a comprehensive report that provides insights into the biomass resources available in a specific region and their potential for various applications. This information can be used by policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the development of biomass-based industries and the implementation of sustainable energy strategies.

Figure 26 Example of an action plan of the portofolio

The Support Action Portfolio is here available: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/support-actions/>

Typology Matrix

The Typology Matrix is a guiding framework that categorizes and clarifies governance models in the circular bioeconomy. It includes a comprehensive overview of regional circular bioeconomy governance strategies in the EU-27. It introduces a typology of regional bioeconomy governance models across ten dimensions, classifying them based on four bio-based transformation paths and two governance functions. The typology, derived from 20 case studies, distinguishes over 15 types of circular bioeconomy governance models, addressing key performance indicators. The typology allows the classification of present and future circular bioeconomy governance models.

The typology matrix is accessible for online viewing or available for download in PDF format for offline consultation (Figure 27).

Figure 27 Screenshot of the typology matrix site

EPP Tool available under: <https://robintoolbox.web.auth.gr/index.php/typology-matrix/>

3.4 Initial toolbox testing

An initial testing of the toolbox functionality was carried out by the ROBIN project partners in WP2. For each toolbox component partners were asked to provide feedback regarding the following aspects:

- **User Interface:** Evaluating the intuitiveness and user-friendliness of the toolbox.

- **Content Accuracy:** Verifying the precision of all digitized toolbox components, including descriptions, explanations, and figures.
- **Functionality:** Assessing whether the digital toolbox executes its functions accurately and efficiently.
- **Suggestions for Improvement:** Soliciting specific recommendations or enhancements from partners.

The feedback, collected in written form by S2I and AUTH, informed subsequent updates and changes, culminating in the completion of the toolbox development within WP2. To further refine the toolbox, additional comprehensive testing rounds are planned for WP3. These forthcoming tests will encompass more specific evaluation factors, such as use purposes, user demographics, user experience, information relevance, content quality, functionality, customization, and adaptability, among others. This testing will play an essential role to further define user roadmaps.

4. Conclusions and next steps

In conclusion, the developments in Tasks 2.3 and 2.4 resulted in the ROBIN digital toolbox, which provides practical information and tools for regional authorities to develop or improve their bioeconomy regional governance models. The Knowledge Platform serves as a comprehensive repository of circular bioeconomy governance models and practical strategies. The three tools – Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, Bioeconomy Policy Monitoring Tool, and Environmental Protection Planning Tool – empower regional policymakers with co-design capabilities, governance assessments, and environmental planning solutions. The inclusion of the Support Action Portfolio (SAP) further enhances the toolbox, offering regions inspirational examples and capacity-building measures.

The digitalization of the toolbox ensured accessibility and user-friendliness, incorporating essential features to enhance efficiency and user experience. To ensure continuous improvement of the ROBIN toolbox and within the scope of future work packages (WP3), alpha and beta testing will be deployed with the regional stakeholders, where the ROBIN team will identify any usability issues, gather initial feedback on the tool's functionality, and understand the user experience in-depth, which is crucial to define specific use roadmaps such as need for information by starting or extending bioeconomy governance models, developing monitoring of policies, determination of funding schemes, etc. The suggestions obtained from the testing will be investigated and integrated into the tool. This process will ensure that the toolbox is not only user-friendly but also tailored to the specific needs and challenges of the bioeconomy policy field.

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Annexes

4.1 ROBIN Toolbox Wireframe- Working document

Main Site

ROBIN Toolbox

Toolbox Deliverables Dissemination material Related projects & initiatives

ROBIN Toolbox is composed of three components supporting the regional partners in implementing their governance models and structures:

1. ROBIN Knowledge Platform including different types of regional bioeconomy governance models and good governance practices.
2. ROBIN Tools for the development of circular bioeconomy governance models, evaluation of the performance of the governance model and detection of non-environmentally friendly practices across environmental management areas.
3. ROBIN Support Actions Portfolio tailored to the needs of the ROBIN regions.

Visit the ROBIN Toolbox

Subsections

Description of the toolbox
- General description of the toolbox (what this do and how)

Structure of the toolbox
- Diagram
- Field with short description of each part when the mouse is on it

```
graph TD;
  A[ROBIN TOOLBOX] --> B[Knowledge Platform];
  A --> C[Tools];
  A --> D[Support Actions Portfolio];
  B --> E[Regional Governance Models];
  B --> F[Good Governance Practices];
  C --> G[Circular Bioeconomy Model Canvas];
  C --> H[Policy Monitoring System];
  D --> I[Environmental Protection Planning Tool];
```

Use guideline (as questionnaire)
short questionnaire to give suggestions to the user which part of the toolbox can be more useful to explore (depending on what they are looking for). For example: Are you looking for examples of Bioeconomy good practices in other regions? → go to “Good Governance [Practices](#)”

Download document roadmap and business models?

Regional Governance Models-RGM (Overview page) *Example*

Title of RGM 1

Country RGM 1 (text) Static map

Type (text)

Title of RGM 2

Short description (2-4 lines)

Country RGM 2 (text) Static map

Type (text)

Title of RGM 3

Short description (2-4 lines)

Country RGM 3 (text) Static map

Type (text)

SEARCH

Search Field

FILTERS Clear Filters

Countries

Dropdown list

Type of strategy

Dropdown list

Type of territorial aspect

Dropdown list

Type of transformation path

Dropdown list

Type of enabling gov. mechanism

Dropdown list

Type of constraining governance

Dropdown list

Type of driver measures

Dropdown list

Type of focus

Dropdown list

Regional Governance Models RGM (Details of each practice) *Structure Example – Example of the content*

Title of GGP 1

Country/ Region
Country/Region name

Executive Summary
Text description (3-4 Lines)

Type of strategy
Type of strategy text

Description
Text description

Key actors
Text

Environmental objectives
Description environmental objectives

Societal objectives
Description objectives

Economic objectives
Description economic objectives

Transformation path
Text

Driver Measures
Text

Enabling Governance Mechanisms
Text

Constrain Governance
Text

Focus
Text

Further Information
e.g. links to websites

Good Governance Practices- GGP (Overview page) *Example*

Title of GGP 1

Short description (2-4 lines)

Country GGP 1 (text)

Type (text)

Title of GGP 2

Short description (2-4 lines)

Country GGP 2 (text)

Type (text)

Title of GGP 3

Short description (2-4 lines)

Country GGP 3 (text)

Type (text)

SEARCH

Search Field

FILTERS

Countries

Dropdown list

Type of practice

Dropdown list

Good Governance Practices GGP (Details of each practice) *Structure Example – Example of the content*

Title of GGP 1

Country/ Region
Country/Region name

Type of practice
Type of practice

Executive Summary
Text description (3-4 Lines)

Description
Text description

Deployment Setting
Type of deployment

Stakeholders/Beneficiaries
Type of stakeholders/Beneficiaries

Environmental Impact
Description environmental impact

Social Impact
Description social impact

Economic Impact
Description economic impact

Further Information
e.g. links to websites

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model

(title)

Text with the explanation on how to use the canvas: The Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas should be seen as a strategic co-creation tool that will allow each region to describe, design, challenge and invent a regional vision, and identify support activities required to implement this vision. This will be specific to each region. This tool can be continuously updated as the region's circular bioeconomy develops.

Graphic of the canvas (as picture/ it is possible a textbox in each field with explanations (when mouse touches the fields?))

Download guidance document (pdf)

Download Canvas (as pdf)

Link Miro template

Download guidance document: [here](#) Download canvas: [here](#) Description canvas: [here](#)

Policy Monitoring Tool (Intro page)

Policy Monitoring Tool

(title)

Short Introduction to the tool

ESG & Territory metrics

Click to select → go to next site:

Environmental

Socioeconomic

Governance

Public
Engagement

Ethics

Policy Monitoring Tool (selected ESG)

Title selected ESG

(title)

Environmental Protection Planning Tool

Environmental Protection Planning Tool

(title)

Short Introduction to the tool

Online Tool

Excel online or Google Sheets → as Template (so the changes made by users are not saved in the online tool)
-The user will be able to fill it in online and then download it, along with its results, to their computer

Download tool (as Excel table)

Guideline (as Excel table)

Actions Portfolio

Support Actions Portfolio
(title)

Short introduction to the tool

Measure 1 title

Short description (2-4 lines)

Type Measure 1 *(text)*

Region Measure 1 *(text)*

Measure 2 title

Short description (2-4 lines)

Type Measure 2 *(text)*

Region Measure 2 *(text)*

SEARCH

Search Field

FILTERS

Type of measure

Dropdown list

Region

Dropdown list

Support Actions Portfolio (each measure page)

Title measure
(title)

Type of measure

text

Description of the measure

text

Robin region

To be clarify with the [regions](#)

[Download Excel table](#)

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the CCRI-CSO. We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

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